

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.12 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5th generation
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ASC	Assisted service continuity
BCR	Benefit-Cost Ratio
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CPM	Cooperative Perception Message
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DbW	Drive By Wire
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
E2E	End-to-End
eMBB	enhanced Mobile BroadBand
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
gNB	Next Generation NodeB
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMD	Head Mounting Device
HOI	Handover Interval
ICS	Intersection Controller System
IP	Intellectual Property
IoT	Internet Of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MAMCA	Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis
MCC	Mobile Country Code
MCC	Mobile Country Code
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNC	Mobile Network Code
MNC	Mobile Network Code
MNO	Mobile Network Operator

Abbreviation / Term	Description
MOS	Mean Opinion Score
MOS-AVQO	Mean Opinion Score - Audio Visual Quality Objective
MOS-AVQS	Mean Opinion Score - Audio Visual Quality Subjective
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEX	Operating Expenses
PCO	Point of Control and Observation
PI	Performance Indicator
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PPS	Pulse Per Second
PR	Penetration Rate
PRI	Penetration Rate Infrastructure
PRV	Penetration Rate Vehicle
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RACH	Random Access Channel
ROI	Return on Investment
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematics
RTT	Round Trip Time
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
STRIA	Strategic Transport Research and Innovation Agenda
SUS	System Usability Scale
SW	Software
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
T&L	Transport and Logistics
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra High Definition
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VR	Virtual Reality
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WTH	Willingness to Have
WTP	Willingness to Pay

1 Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CCAM (Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility) applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CCAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of the Testing Framework deliverables is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems. Deliverable D1.7 gave an initial description of the test framework at the start of the project. This deliverable, D1.12, provides an update, including the procedures for collecting data. The final version of this report (deliverable D1.8) will consolidate insights from the field trials' execution, providing a reference framework for CCAM services validation.

The testing framework builds on the expertise and the results of other projects, as described in D1.7 and consists of two parts: the technical performance evaluation framework and the business evaluation assessment framework. The original project plan was to use the iterative Plan-Do-Check-Act approach, including 3 cycles for the technical validation, with 2 local trial cycles and one wider large-scale trial cycle covering the whole corridor. However, due to changes in the project and delays in the availability of 5G SA roaming, only a single trial cycle is planned. This trial cycle will consist of two short phases: a first phase, concentrating on simple scenarios focusing on measuring service disruption during cross-border and validating the integration of the use cases with the CAM Services Platform. In the second phase, the more complex use case scenarios will be evaluated, e.g., a platoon of several vehicles crossing the border.

During these trials, the KPIs of each use case will be calculated, and they will illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application behaviour. Both terrestrial use cases and maritime use cases will be trialled. The terrestrial use case trials will be performed near the border crossing between Estonia- Latvia and at the Bikernieki racing track in Riga, where a virtual border has been set up. The maritime use case trials are planned to be take place on a ferry between Tallinn and Helsinki.

Further the report describes the data collection process. Starting from the list of KPIs, which are defined in D1.9, the data to be collected by the different components in the trials are identified. For the technical validation, data will be collected from the network, vehicles and from the other equipment used in the project. Measurements will be performed both at application level and at transport level. At transport level, KPIs will be collected using special tools like Keysight Nemo and Qosium. The Tenant Web Portal will assist in starting the measurements and also offers possibilities to upload the data at the end of the experiment and to visualise the KPIs.

The business validation process is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem. Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment. The commercialisation validation process uses a 4-step methodology: customer validation, solutions alignment, business model selection and growth trajectory. The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the - adapted to the project needs – Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) methodology that will result to a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases.

This deliverable also includes the structure of the test plan, which will be developed further for all use cases prior to starting the evaluation. Last, D1.12 describes how the different use cases plan to perform testing and provides the conclusions to be considered for the next steps of the project implementation.

2 Introduction

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CCAM applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki) spanning across three EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CCAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways and shipways throughout Europe.

The scope of this deliverable is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.

2.1 Mapping 5G ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.12	<i>Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0</i>	<i>This document</i>	<i>Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0</i>
TASKS			
T1.4 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	<i>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management.</i>	<i>Section 3</i>	<i>High level description of the technological and the business validation framework</i>
	<i>The testing framework will entail acceptance test procedures for conducting both the technological and business validation of the use cases considering the associated service management.</i>	<i>3.4, 4</i>	<i>Section 3.4 describes business validation acceptance tests; quality of technical performance tests is addressed in chapter 4</i>

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<i>In particular, as far as the technological validation is concerned, we will define the procedures for collecting the data feeds from the 5G nodes, stating also how these feeds will be used and analysed by the Tenant Web Portal to produce and present the KPI values in a graphical form.</i>	4.3	<i>Section 4.3 discusses data collection processes. The Tenant Web Portal is described in D2.7.</i>
	<i>Threshold limits for the benchmarking of the results will also be defined per target KPI based on the requirements stemming from each CCAM use case.</i>	N/A	<i>Target values for the KPIs are discussed in D1.9</i>
	<i>The methodology will also define how the interaction with the CCAM end-users will be achieved taking into consideration the specificities of task T1.1.</i>	4.6	<i>Section 4.6 discusses the Interaction with end-users during technical performance and business validation.</i>
	The business validation process is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem.	3.4	<i>The methodology for the identification of solutions with the highest commercialisation potential is outlined in 3.4.</i>

5G ROUTES GA Component Title	5G ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<p>Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment. The commercialisation validation process uses a 4-step methodology: customer validation, solutions alignment, business model selection and growth trajectory. The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the - adapted to the project needs – Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) methodology that will result to a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases.</p>	3.4, 4.4, 4.6	<p><i>Business validation methodology is described in 3.4 The business KPIs to be used for the evaluation of the business perspective of the use cases are described in section 4.4. Questionnaires, surveys and workshop material for business validation are described in section 4.6.</i></p>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

2.2.1 Scope of the Testing Framework

The scope of the testing framework deliverables (D1.7, D1.12, D1.8) is to define the methodology and the toolset for both the technological performance and business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems. The testing framework consists of two parts: the technical performance evaluation framework and the business evaluation assessment framework.

The main purpose of the technical performance evaluation framework is to define the processes for data collection and analysis for the technical evaluation of the use cases in cross-border scenarios. The framework determines the data to be collected, and how the KPIs are calculated from the collected data.

The business evaluation assessment framework engages and examines the field trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem.

2.2.2 Relation to Other Deliverables

This deliverable describes the testing framework, addressing both technical performance evaluation and business validation. Figure 1 shows the relation between the work described in this deliverable and other project deliverables.

The report builds on the work, described in Deliverables D1.1 [1], D1.9 [4], D1.3 [2] and D1.5 [3]. Deliverables D1.1 and D1.9 describe the use cases, scenarios and KPIs, for both technical performance and business values, and their target values. Deliverable D1.3 describes the 5G network requirements, architecture and the deployment in the trial sites. Deliverable D1.5 analyses how the use cases benefit from 5G, describes the network level KPIs and the test measurements.

From D1.1, the specific features of use cases, such as the components required, situational variables and possibility to involve test users, are to be taken into account when designing the methodology. The KPIs affect the network requirements, and hence the 5G functionalities which will be included in the 5G test network at the trial sites. This work is described in D1.3. The network architecture and its deployment in the test site affects to the use case scenarios, and to the test framework. D1.5 provides initial information on how the network level KPIs must be measured.

Deliverable D1.7 [5] provided the first version of the test framework. This work was used as input for D2.7 [7] on the Tenant Web Portal and for D5.1 [6], which describes the methodology to be employed across the commercialisation and market development activities for the exploitable outputs from 5G-ROUTES. The Tenant Web Portal will enable real-time graph data presentation and provide visualisation of the KPIs. Deliverable D2.7 [7] also describes the format to be used for the collection of data.

Deliverable D1.12, this document, is the second version of the testing framework report, and includes updates based on the work described in D5.1 and D2.7.

The output of this work will be used in D4.1, where the test scenarios and the test plans will be described, as well as in D5.2, which will describe the impact assessment and cost benefit analysis.

The procedures mentioned in this report, including the data collection procedures for the use cases, are tested during the lab trials, reported in D3.8. The testing framework will then be used for the first evaluation runs during the first set of trials, which will be reported in D4.3. The procedures may then be refined based on the experiences during the evaluation, reported in D4.6. The specifications of the different data collection procedures will then be reported in the final version of the testing framework. The network related indicators will be collected, according to D1.5, and evaluated and reported in D3.2.

Figure 1: Relation between D1.12 and other deliverables

2.2.3 Deliverable Structure

Chapter 3 gives a high-level outline of the testing framework for both the technical performance evaluation procedures and business validation. It also addresses the data collection and KPI visualisation procedures. Especially CCAM automated driving use cases set requirements to the development and testing environment, which have to be taken into account during testing and data collection.

Chapter 4 discusses the data collection. The procedures for collecting the data for the technical performance evaluation is described. The data to be collected for the technical performance evaluation and the business assessment are analysed. The involvement of users and the tools for collecting information from end-users and stakeholders are described.

Chapter 5 gives a general overview of the test plan, which will be elaborated in more detail in D4.1, prior to starting the field trials.

Chapter 6 gives an overview of the different use cases, which data will be collected and where the trials are planned.

Chapter 7 draws the conclusions of this report, indicates the next steps towards the assessment and the requirements to the data collection system.

3 Testing Framework Overview

This section will give an overview of the framework.

The testing framework in 5G-ROUTES is based on the frameworks for the validation and benchmarking of results from previous relevant projects, including:

- 5G-SOLUTIONS [9], a 5G-PPP project using a testing framework based on the Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle [10];
- 5G-TOURS [11] and 5G-EVE [12], 5G PPP projects;
- 5G-MOBIX [13], a 5G-PPP project on cross-border CCAM;
- FESTA [14];
- TRUSTS [15], a H2020 project using the same iterative approach as 5G-ROUTES.

These testing frameworks are described in D1.7.

3.1 Testing Framework Concept

The original approach of the 5G-ROUTES project was based on three iterative cycles of development and testing, based on Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act approach [10]. The phases of the Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act are mapped in 5G-ROUTES as:

- **Plan:** design of the use case. During this phase both the use case is defined, and the test cases are defined.
- **Do:** development and testing in lab trials. The use case functionalities are developed and tested in laboratory conditions. In parallel the infrastructure and the required network functionalities are deployed at the trial sites. The evaluation plan for the trial phase is elaborated. The data collection and evaluation tools are validated.
- **Check:** trial execution and data collection in the trials.
- **Act:** evaluation and formulation of improvements.

For these reasons there are two types of tests in 5G-ROUTES:

- **Technical testing in lab trials.** The purpose of the lab trials is to test the functionalities and the readiness of the use cases in restricted closed areas, as well as to test the integration of the use cases with the enablers from the CAM Services Platform, which are developed in WP2 and described in D2.1 [16] and D2.9 [8]. The lab trials aim to address most of the challenges, minimize the risks and reduce the uncertainties before the large-scale field trials are set and executed.
- **Field trials** will validate the capabilities of both the 5G technology and the use cases so as to enable their commercial exploitation. During the project the use cases will validate 5G enabling technologies' features and capabilities in the cross-border areas (i.e., Valga/Valka, Tallinn-Helsinki ferry. As well as at a virtual border, which has been set up at the Bikernieki racetrack in Riga).

During the course of the project the focus of the project was changed on request of the European Commission, and this, resulting with technical challenges related to the availability of 5G SA roaming, resulted in several rescheduling phases in the project. A major change in refocusing of the use cases, which are described in D1.1 [1], is the concentration on two ecosystems:

- Terrestrial ecosystem, consisting of the following use cases:
 - I. **See-through platooning.** This use case builds on UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC1.3.
 - II. **Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving.** This use case builds on UC2.1, UC3.1 and a refocused UC3.3.
 - III. **Infotainment: Real-time virtual collaboration and gaming.**
 - UC4.1: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go
 - UC4.2: 3D Real-time virtual collaboration on the move
- Maritime ecosystem, in which the following use cases are trialled:
 - UC4.1: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.
 - UC 5.1: Connected logistics.
 - UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border

The original first set of trials with 5G NSA, which was planned for Autumn 2022, was discarded in order to reserve sufficient resources for 5G SA tests. The trials will be concentrated in 2024, when the 5G network infrastructure, with a Local Breakout roaming solution is available, consisting of two short trial phases:

- for the Maritime ecosystem:
 - in a first phase, the tests are concentrated on assessing the validity of the technical solution for multi-hop;
 - in the second phase the selected use cases are evaluated.
- for the Terrestrial ecosystem:
 - the first phase involves basic scenarios and is concentrated on the assessment of service disruption and to validate the interaction with the CAM Services Platform;
 - second trial run with large field trials.

The technical KPIs of each use case will be evaluated during the different trial cycles, to illustrate how 5G capabilities and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers are leveraged and how they impact application behaviour.

KPIs and their target values have been specified for the different use cases in D1.1 [1] and D1.9 [4]. The impact of 5G technologies and 5G-ROUTES technical enablers on the KPIs will be measured and quantified. A special emphasis will be placed on service continuity, especially on the disruption of the service during handovers between 5G telecom operators. Multiple cross-border scenarios will be tested in field trials, involving both terrestrial and maritime environments. Conclusions and recommendations will be drawn including recommendations for further trial validations. When possible, the impact of 5G deployment will be also analysed so to potentially allow operators to evaluate their 5G network deployment scope, pattern, and duration.

3.2 Key Performance Indicators and Data Collection

Deliverable D1.1 describes the use cases and their requirements. Based on these requirements, the required performance of the network is derived in D1.5 and the targets for the network level Performance Indicators (PIs).

In deliverable D1.9, for each of the use cases, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are identified to measure the success of the use cases, as well as their target values. KPIs are both defined at application level for the technical performance and related to business aspects., as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: KPIs in 5G-ROUTES

The following types of KPIs can be identified:

- **Network level PIs**, which are agnostic to the use cases. The targets for these network PIs are calculated so, that the use case target KPIs can be fulfilled. Network PIs and their measurements are described in D1.5 [3]. The results of the measurements and the evaluation will be reported in D3.2. KPIs will be selected from the measured performance indicators and described in D1.6.
- Use case specific **technical KPIs**. Starting from the data collected during the use case trials, PIs for assessing the technical performance at service level are calculated, such as latencies of the different legs of the 5G delivery chain. The value of the PI may depend upon the configuration of the 5G network, the enablers used and potentially environmental variables (such as weather) and situational variables, such as the speed of the vehicles. Special attention will also be put on the effect of border crossing and handover.

PIs, which are identified as important for the evaluation of the technical performance of the use case, are fed as KPIs into the Tenant Web Portal [7]. These indicators are compared to threshold values, set in D1.9, and provide the satisfaction level of the KPIs. The satisfaction level of different indicators is then combined to form a Composite Indicator, which represents the satisfaction level for the use case, and these are visualised in the Tenant Web Portal.

The technical PIs are mainly calculated from measured data, but data from users' feedback is used to some extent, e.g., for the Quality of Experience (QoE) KPI. The framework for collecting and analysing the data is described in section 3.3.

The results of the evaluation during the different trial phases will be reported in D4.6.

- **Business KPIs**, which are calculated from input obtained from stakeholder interactions, such as focus groups and interviews. The framework for business validation is described in section 3.4. The results of the business assessment will be reported in D5.2.

3.3 Technical Performance Evaluation Framework Concept

The data needed for the technical performance evaluation will be collected at local sites and the large-scale tests, and potentially at the lab trials, dependent on the nature of the use case and the availability of resources (network functionalities, vehicles, infrastructure sensors).

3.3.1 General Test Process

There are two sets of lab trial runs and one set of field trials in 5G-ROUTES:

- Lab trial#1 in 2022, when preparing the use cases for the 5G NSA field trial run, which was planned in 2022, but cancelled due to refocusing of the project.
- Lab trial#2 in 2023, when preparing for the field trials which take place in early 2024.

Figure 3: Timetable of lab trials and field trials in 5G-ROUTES

3.3.1.1 Test Process Phases

The process for technical performance testing consists of the following phases:

- During use case development, each use case integrates logging of the data at application level. APIs are made available for uploading of the data to the Tenant Web Portal, which is described in D2.7 [7]. The data are either uploaded using the Tenant Web Portal functionality or manually.
- During the first set of lab tests, the different functionalities of the use case, are verified. Verification takes place in 5G test networks, close to the developers’ facilities, or in commercial 4G/5G networks. The data collection mechanisms are validated.
- The pilot readiness is verified at the end of the lab trial phase in Spring 2022, through assessment that all the equipment, data communications and logging, software and algorithms are working as planned. Remote verification techniques are used to check the interfaces between the different components and the access to the networks at the large-scale trial sites. The results of the first round of lab trials and field operational readiness are reported in D3.8.
- A second run of lab trials takes place in 2023. During these lab trials, focus is on the integration of the use cases with CAM services and the enablers of the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform, as well as on cross-border issues. The second run of lab trials are reported in D3.9.
- The first phase of the 5G SA field trials will be concentrated on detailed measurement for basic functionalities of the use cases, especially regarding the cross-border behaviour. More details on the trial sites are provided in Section 3.3.4. The scenarios, which will be tested in the field trials are reported in D4.1. Network level PIs are collected using the measurement methods reported in D1.5 [3]. During the trial experiments are performed and data for the technical performance evaluation are collected. Based on the collected data, the use case specific technical PIs are calculated, and the evaluation results will be reported in D4.6.
- The use cases are then implemented and evaluated during the second phase of the field trials. The trials are reported in D4.5, and the evaluation results in D4.6.

- The experiences during the field trials run are used to produce D1.8, the final version of the testing framework report (this report).

3.3.1.2 *Baseline and Impact of Configurations*

The main aim of the technical performance evaluation is to test the impact of 5G and the solutions developed by 5G-ROUTES on the integrated CCAM use cases. Technical performance evaluations measure the improvement of new technology and tools compared to a baseline situation.

The baseline for the terrestrial use cases is the case without the deployed CAM Services Platform. For this purpose the CAM services and the enablers which are essential to perform the use case will be deployed on the cloud or at servers outside of the mobile network.

During technical performance evaluation, different configurations of the network may be tested, and the impact of technological choices on the performance of the use cases will be monitored. During the different trials, different network configurations and use case algorithm versions can be evaluated, e.g., the use of slicing for reserving resources for different use case functionalities.

3.3.1.3 *Test Logistics*

The nature of the use cases, i.e., cross-border CCAM including automated driving, poses additional challenges to the testing. Cross-border 5G scenarios involve networks of two different MNOs. Border crossings are not located near the research and development facilities, hence on-site testing involves travelling of both research personnel and the equipment, such as the research vehicle prototypes.

Another issue is the frequency of border crossings, especially for maritime traffic. For road crossings, vehicles can be driven over a cross-border route, which crosses the border multiple times within a short period of time. Ferries, however, have a fixed timetable and cross the border only a few times a day (e.g., Eckerö Finbo crosses the border 4-6 times per day).

For the trials of the automated driving use cases, prototype vehicles are used, and both access to the vehicles as well as testing facilities are restricted. For these reasons, initial testing of the use cases is performed at facilities, to which the researchers have easy access, and then validated at the cross-border sites.

The performance of the trials may pose several logistical issues, such as:

- trial demonstrations are resource intensive. They involve expensive equipment which must be brought on site by the project partners, such as instrumented vehicles, requiring time and resources for travel to the trial site. The first phase of the trials will use simple scenarios, concentrating on 5G connectivity. Instead of an On-Board Unit (OBU) integrated in vehicles, equipment which can be easily placed in vehicles from other partners or rental vehicles will be used. In addition, the scenarios involve only one vehicle with 2 OBUs in a single vehicle or one moving and one static OBU.
- testing of automated driving requires permits needed for operation of the vehicle on public roads in both Estonia and Latvia, as well as the permit of the local authorities to use the road. Hence, to avoid this issue, automated operation of the vehicles will be performed as much as possible on closed roads. In order to be able to test automated driving safely and to be able to perform frequent handover events, a virtual border has been set up at the Bikernieki racetrack in Riga, which is closed to public traffic.
- some automated vehicles use cases cannot be safely demonstrated in winter. Snow and ice affect the dynamic behaviour of the vehicle, and reduce the visibility of lane and road markings, on which vehicle sensors rely.

For these reasons, trials of the automotive use cases will be concentrated in specific test sessions, which are limited in time. The closure of the road must be agreed with the local authorities. Discussions have been started with local authorities, and the national authorities are positive towards the tests. Dependent on the received permits, the trials of the automated driving use cases will be concentrated in test sessions with a duration of one day to two weeks.

3.3.2 Lab Trial Locations

The lab trial locations are described in D1.7 [5]. The results of the lab tests will be reported in D3.8 and D3.9.

The main purpose of the lab trials is to assure that the use case will work when deployed at the trial sites. During the first set of lab trials, mostly locations near to the facilities of the use case developers are used. These include:

- Bikernieki racetrack, Latvia;
- Pirkkala karting track and VTT 5G test network in Otaniemi and Oulu, Finland;
- Satory, France;
- CTTC testbed in Barcelona, Spain.
- TTU 5G testbed in Tallinn, Estonia

In order to test the use cases in a lab environment, the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform will be deployed in CTTC 5G testbed, and the integration of the use cases with the 5G-ROUTES CAM Services Platform will be tested remotely during the second lab trial run.

3.3.3 Scenarios for the field trials

The use cases of the project, described in D1.1 [1], are combined in two ecosystems, as mentioned in Section 3.1. In both ecosystems: the maritime and the terrestrial ecosystem. Field trials will be executed in two phases. The first phase consists of simplified scenarios, in which the basic functionalities of the use cases are tested, with focus on service continuity and validation of the network solution. The simplified scenarios include:

1. The Maritime ecosystem will implement a technical solution for multi-hop. It is tested using fixed network and a single User Equipment (UE), with exchange of video between the UE in the network and a fixed node. This configuration will be also stressed employing one of the Infotainment use case where high frequency messaging (60 or 120 Hz) will challenge the network latency.
2. The Terrestrial ecosystem consists of 4 use cases, as mentioned in Section 3.1. For the first set of trials, only the basic functionalities of the use cases will be tested. Focus in the first trials is on assessment of service continuity and service disruption when crossing the border. These are the considerations for the different use cases:
 - **I. See-through platooning.** The use case relies on CAM services, which follow the leading UE when crossing the border. So, when the leading UE of a fleet crosses the border, the CAM service has been proactively instantiated in the visiting network. The data exchanged consists of both video (UC1.3) and short V2X data packets which are transmitted every 50-100 ms (UC1.1, UC1.2). For this first use case the tests in the first trial will be concentrated on the exchange of video between a UE crossing the border and another UE, using the enablers from the CAM Services Platform and a video proxy CAM service.
 - **II. Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving.** The data exchanged between the different UEs and the CAM Services Platform are V2X messages transmitted every 100 ms (similar to the data exchanged in UC1.1 and UC1.2). The tests in the first trial will hence consist of exchanging V2X messages between UEs in the different networks. The use case makes use of location-dependent CAM services, e.g., for situational awareness, which should

communicate with the UE in identical way at both sides of the border and should provide the same level of service to the UE at both sides of the border.

- **UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go.** The simplified scenario deals with transmission of gaming data between game server and a single UE (smart phone or tablet) crossing the border. A main difference to the other simplified scenarios is that the UE does not have the advanced position and timing capabilities of the automotive UEs.
- **UC4.2 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move.** The simplified scenario deals with transmission of stereoscopic video data between a streaming fixed station and a receiving moving laptop with a connected head mounted display (HMD). A main difference to the other simplified scenarios is that the UE employed does not have positioning capabilities and will employ network positioning data.

In Chapter 6, a brief overview of both the simplified test scenarios and the use-case test scenarios for each of the use cases is given. The scenarios will be described in more detail in D4.1.

3.3.4 Trial Sites

3.3.4.1 Road Border Crossing between Estonia and Latvia in Valga

The E264 crosses the border between Latvia and Estonia in the twin city of Valga/Valka. Figure 4 shows the border crossing of the E264 (Rujienas street (LV)). Near the border crossing there is an intersection: the motorway continues to the left (Transpordi street) in Figure 4, and the road to the right (Viljandi street) leads to the centre of Valga. The E264 motorway is a two-way road with one lane in each direction without central barrier. The other border crossings between Latvia and Estonia in Ikla and Tsiiruli are on similar two-way roads.

Figure 4: Border crossing between Latvia and Estonia on the E264 (in Google Maps)

For the use case II, intelligent traffic lights have been installed at intersections of the E264: at the intersection Rujienas street – Viljandi street – Transpordi street in Estonia, and at the intersection of Rujienas-Ausekla street on the Latvian side. The test site is described in more detail in D3.1, section 4.2 [19].

Use cases I and II involve also autonomous driving. For assuring the safety of all road participants, the road should be closed for other traffic during the testing of these use cases. For testing these use cases, the following conditions need to be fulfilled:

- the road must be suitable for testing of the use cases (e.g., required amount number of lanes), and sufficiently long length to be able to perform the manoeuvre;
- the area should be covered by the 5G communication infrastructure;
- the road authorities provide the permission to close the road.

Automated driving tests will only be performed during the final phase of trials. During the first trial phase the main focus is on the communication between vehicles, and only during the second phase of the trials the roads will be closed for other traffic and the automated driving functionalities will be trialled.

5G Network Configuration

The network in Valga/Valka is developed taking the needs of the project into account and is described in more detail in D3.1, section 4.2 [19].

Test Vehicles

Prototype vehicles will be provided by EDI, VEDECOM and VTT. The vehicles are equipped with On-Board Units (OBUs) with 5G communications, environmental perception sensors and the vehicles have automated driving capabilities. During the trials, OBUs provided by partners may be installed in vehicles from EDI or in rental vehicles to test 5G communications for CCAM. An overview of the vehicles is provided in D3.3 [20] .

Trialling CCAM in Valga

The use cases I and II from the Terrestrial Ecosystem will be trialled in Valga. Some of the scenarios of this use case, such as the simplified scenario for service disruption testing, may also be executed in the Bikernieki trial site, which is described in the next section.

3.3.4.2 Riga Bikernieki Racing circuit

A virtual border is set up in the Bikernieki Racing circuit in Riga. Both LMT and Telia Estonia have installed a 5G-base station at the racing circuit, which will allow to test handover between networks. The test site is described in more detail in D3.1, section 4.1[19].

Use case I (See-through platooning) may be evaluated in Bikernieki.

3.3.4.3 Ferry between Tallinn and Helsinki

A mobile 5G base station is planned to be installed into a ferry of Eckerö Line. Eckerö Line operates two vessels between Helsinki and Tallinn for both passengers and freight: M/S Finlandia, between the Länsisatama port in Helsinki and the A-Terminal in Tallinn, and M/S Finbo Cargo, between Vuosaari port, on the outskirts of Helsinki, and the port of Muuga Harbour near Tallinn. M/S Finbo is mainly targeted towards freight transport but can also carry 300 passengers. The vessel makes daily 2-3 trips between Helsinki and Tallinn in each direction.

Figure 5: Vessel M/s Finbo Cargo from Eckerö Line (eckeroline.fi)

5G Network Configuration

The planned 5G network for the ferry use cases is discussed in more detail in D3.1, section 4.4 [19]. The equipment on board of the Finbo vessel will be updated for 5G communications. In addition, a satellite receiver will be installed on the ferry, as detailed in D3.3 [20]. The equipment will be used to demonstrate multi-hop, which will be described in D1.13.

Use Case Testing on the Ferry

The use cases from the Maritime Ecosystem will be evaluated on the ferry:

- **UC5.1 Connected logistics**
- **UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border**
- **UC4.1 Immersive 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go**

3.3.5 Ecosystem Specific Overview

Table 2 gives an overview of the tests for the different use cases and clusters, giving a summary of the vehicles which have to be brought to the trial site, the location of the lab trials, the nature of the trial, and the location of trials.

Table 2: Overview of trial locations in 5G-ROUTES

UC	UC title	Vehicle Provider	Lab test	Trials
Terrestrial Ecosystem				
I.	See-through platooning and logistics	EDI, VTT	Bikernieki, VTT-Otaniemi	Valga/Valka and/or Bikernieki
II.	Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving	VEDECOM, VTT, EDI	Versailles, Tampere, TTU	Valga/Valka
4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go		Barcelona	Valga/Valka
4.2	3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go		Barcelona	
Maritime Ecosystem				
5.1	Connected logistics	Vediafi Eckerö – ferry	Vedia lab/ Otaniemi Tallinn	Ferry Helsinki (Vuosaari) – Tallinn (Muuga)
5.2	Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border	Eckerö – ferry	Athens	
4.1	360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go	Eckerö – ferry	Barcelona	

3.4 Business Evaluation Assessment Framework

3.4.1 Business Evaluation Goals

The business validation process in 5G-ROUTES is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens. This will help identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders of the two 5G-ROUTES ecosystems; the maritime and the terrestrial.

Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment.

The ultimate goal for **the commercialisation validation process** in WP5 is to create anticipatory business plans for two solutions, one for each of the two ecosystems, that extend 5G at different cross-border environments. A customer-focused, collaborative and iterative process has been designed that helps to guide the solution providers from initial ideas through to potential business impact and demonstrate how commercial actors supporting the ecosystems could move those outputs closer to commercial reality.

For the **business impact assessment**, we will work upon the defined two ecosystems (maritime and terrestrial), in order to collect the required data during stakeholder workshops and interviews. The collected data will be both quantitative (i.e., costs) and qualitative as reflected by the selected Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) business criteria. The cost benefit analysis and business impact assessment will be formulated based on future penetration scenarios on the validated most promising business opportunities. The final outcome of T5.2 will be to deliver the estimated impact and cost-benefit for the developed ecosystems, validated by both internal and external to the project stakeholders. Furthermore, on the basis of the 5G Architecture and 5G CAM Infrastructure developed in the project, we will investigate the interoperability impact and deployment potential in close collaboration with the project technology providers.

More details about the business validation methodology and results will be reported in the new D5.2 (merged D5.2 and D5.3) “Business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems”.

The overall business validation methodology has many key activities and actions to ultimately arrive at providing practical commercial recommendations to the consortium and the 5G for CCAM European community:

- i. create a detailed assessment of broad market opportunities and the evolving technological, financial and social environment surrounding 5G and cross-border networking aspects;
- ii. undertake an analysis of the business opportunities for the two 5G ROUTES ecosystems (maritime and terrestrial);
- iii. arrive to two business propositions (one for each ecosystem: maritime and terrestrial) on making 5G a reliable and high-quality technology even at the border between two countries and administrative domains;
- iv. evaluate the value propositions for the two ecosystems through stakeholder workshops (one for each ecosystem) to identify the priority areas for the cost-benefit analysis;
- v. perform business impact assessment and cost-benefit analyses for the two ecosystems supported by stakeholder ecosystems’ interviews;
- vi. assign each commercial service with a lead commercialisation partner around whom the business development plan that is created within 5G-ROUTES can be centred;
- vii. expand each ecosystem sufficiently to understand key dynamics around revenue, cost, investment etc. for each ecosystem and ultimately prepare the final business models for potential implementation post project completion.

It is noted that Innovation Management play a supporting role in business validation by helping partners identify the unique value proposition along with the potential competitive advantage and business prospect of an

innovative idea. This idea is documented in the Innovation Registry (a tool facilitating Innovation Management) where it is linked with potential business benefits (e.g., cost-efficiency, increased market reach, new functionalities, improved quality of service, etc). Furthermore, through IP Protection and the patenting process -the filing of 4 patents is funded through 5G-ROUTES- innovative ideas are legally protected thus restricting competition in the specific domain. The methodology and results of the Innovation Management and IP (Intellectual Property) protection is reported in D5.5 “Innovation Management Plan and IP protection report v1.0” and in D5.6 “Innovation management plan and IP protection report final version”.

3.4.2 5G-ROUTES Commercialisation Validation and Acceleration Methodology

In an European Research Project context, the consortium is in many ways restricted compared to standalone, individual start-ups who seek to address specific problems for a narrow customer segment and grow outwards from an initial pilot implementation to long-term viability. EU research projects, by their nature, must take a broader view that encompasses a range of views and expertise to finally arrive at a body of knowledge that can be transformative for the future of EU citizens. **Nonetheless, the challenge remains to keep research focused on creating solutions that create value for real stakeholders.**

Table 3 provides a high-level view of the 4 pillars of the methodology and the process involved in moving towards a validated, commercially viable plan for those opportunities that are the most commercially attractive. The specific tasks, methods and tools employed in each phase are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Tasks, methods and tools in commercialisation validation

Goal **Create a body of work that provides a realistic roadmap for the commercialisation of outputs from the research project that are customer oriented, validated and supported by commercially motivated consortium partners.**

Phase	Customer Validation	Solution Alignment	Business Model Selection	Growth Trajectory
Key Question	Segment and refine specific customer wants and needs	Define and align potential product(s) to target market	Select most appropriate business model to acquire and retain profitable customers	Articulate a business plan for growth and sustainability
Key Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market / stakeholder analysis and segmentation Ecosystem focused business validation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agree product(s) to commercialise/exploit with commercial leader(s) Define product and service portfolio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine range of potential models Align business model to commercial leader and early adopters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roadmaps – financial, people, product, marketing, sales, funding
Methods and Tools	Questionnaires, solution provider interviews	Product definition workshops, commercial leader workshops	Business model workshops, business model canvas, value proposition canvas, PESTLE analysis	Financial templates, commercial leader Interviews

3.4.3 Business Impact Assessment Methodology

The Business impact assessment of 5G-ROUTES will be based on the analysis of the business models and value propositions through the application of the – adapted to the project needs – MAMCA methodology. This will result to a broad screening of the business opportunities and their ranking, followed by a **Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)** that will evaluate in-depth the present value of the benefit streams for the selected business cases. The involvement of the internal and external stakeholders identified preliminary in D1.1 and D1.9 and revisited within WP5 will serve a major role in the process. The results of this work will be reported in D5.2.

The business impact indicators will be recreated to focus more on the 5G technology improvements for the two project ecosystems. This is a part of the Step 3 of the MAMCA methodology (see below Figure 6) that feed the CBA for the in-depth analysis. MAMCA methodology uses as its main tool physical stakeholder workshops (see Section 4.6.2.2) for each identified business ecosystem, in order to weigh the business criteria at first and then to rank the value propositions against those criteria. Two physical stakeholder workshops will be realised to evaluate the VPs created for each project ecosystem (maritime and terrestrial).

The MAMCA [21] methodology allows to assess and prioritise a set of alternatives (measures, scenarios, strategies, technological solutions etc.), taking into consideration the opinion of experts as well as the preferences of stakeholders. Apart from resulting in the final prioritisation of the proposed alternatives, the MAMCA methodology allows the understanding of the view of each stakeholder cluster regarding the problem and aims at determining an optimum compromise between the different and usually conflicting stakeholders' interests.

The different steps of the MAMCA methodology are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The MAMCA methodology [33].

CBAs are often used to support decision-making in the context of large-scale infrastructure projects where actual measured data can be gathered during a longer period of time and the piloting phase also provides information about various cost categories during the trial.

For CBAs in the project, qualitative and explorative methodology will be used in addition to tangible data, in order to investigate the potential of the 5G technology in the CCAM markets. To support the qualitative analysis, a set of additional tools will be used (see Section 4.6.2) to facilitate the process, encompassing stakeholder questionnaires and interviews. Such data will be also processed to the sensitivity analysis in order to better define social benefits. This viewpoint emphasizes the significance of identifying solutions for interoperability and potential operators for data-driven services.

As a summary, Figure 7 shows the updated timeline and the different phases of both the commercialisation validation (blue) and the business impact assessment (green).

Figure 7: Phases and timeline of the business validation.

4 Data Collection

4.1 Use Cases, Scenarios and Experiments

The Tenant Web Portal, described in D2.7 [7], will be used for the data storage. The Tenant Web Portal database for collected raw data is structured as follows:

1. Use cases and agnostic data:
 - a. network data is stored in a flat structure in the Tenant Web Portal, and PIs are measured, according to D1.5, for the different networks;
 - b. use cases are characterised by the identifiers previously used, such as UC1.3.
2. Scenarios: for each of the use cases, several test scenarios are defined in D1.9. From measurement viewpoint, a scenario is characterised by the following parameters:
 - i. network configuration(s) used in the test. For cross-border tests this will include 2 networks;
 - ii. use of enablers, including edge, slicing as well as the technical enablers of the CAM Service Platform, developed in 5G-ROUTES;
 - iii. test conditions, including traffic status (test route, road users involved in the test, target speeds), environmental conditions (road weather, vegetation...)

The high-level scenarios in D1.9 [4] will be extended to cover the different variations in network configuration and enabler use. A detailed description of the test scenarios is provided in D4.1 .

3. Experiments: each scenario is repeated several times, under exactly the same conditions.

4.2 Research Questions and Hypotheses

For each of the use cases, a set of target KPIs have been defined in D1.9 [4]. The main research questions addressed in 5G-ROUTES are related to the capability of 5G network and the 5G-ROUTES enablers to reach the target KPI in cross-border environments, and to assure the service continuity without disruption when crossing borders. The main research questions and hypotheses for the use case are addressed in Chapter 6 for each of the use cases.

4.3 Data Collection Process and KPI Visualisation

4.3.1 Data Collection Process of the Use Cases

For the technical performance evaluation, data will be collected from the different 5G nodes involved in the use case trials, including CAM Services Platform, application servers, vehicles and other UEs.

The Tenant Web Portal, which is developed during the 5G-ROUTES project, will be used for storage of the data and for visualising the KPI results [7]. The use of the Tenant Web Portal is considered as an important element to 5G-ROUTES to automate and accelerate the execution of the use cases running in parallel. The Tenant Web Portal is also used for the analysis, benchmarking and presentation of the technical PIs from cross-border field trials. The Tenant Web Portal allows, by using big-data graph analytics and cloud-computing, rapid and automated processing of the vast amount of data obtained from the trials.

The actual raw test data will be stored in the Tenant Web Portal or by the partner responsible for the test (MNO for agnostic tests, use case leader for use case specific tests). Test data with assured quality which has been used for evaluation, will be made available after the project in public repositories like Zenodo.

The Tenant Web Portal will offer the following functionalities [7]:

- Use case setup: making network resources (computing, memory, storage) available for the execution of the use case prior to the actual tests. This includes the instantiation of the CAM services and the assignment of a unique test identifier for the experiment.
- Data storage. The Tenant Web Portal contains a database with both general information on the tests performed, the raw test data collected and the PIs.
- Data collection and storage: Data for the agnostic network measurements is collected using specific tools by the network operators. For the use case specific tests, data can be collected in two ways:
 - automated data collection. The Tenant Web Portal contains an MQTT client, connected to the Integration Fabric enabler described in D2.1 [16], which can inform to the use case devices when the experiment starts and stops. At the end of the experiment, data collected during an experiment can be automatically uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal.
 - manual data collection. Data is collected locally at the different devices and components involved in the CCAM trials. After each specific experiment – or alternatively after the scenario test or at the end of the day, data is manually uploaded to Tenant Web Portal.
- Data download functionality. Use case leaders can download the data collected for quality assurance and analysis.
- KPI input functionality: the test responsible enters the values of the KPIs in the Tenant Web Portal.
- The KPIs are visualised in the Tenant Web portal: the composite indicators, defined in D1.9 [4], are calculated in the Tenant Web Portal, using targets set by the use case leaders, and visualised in a spider graph.

Figure 8 gives an overview of the interaction of the end user (e.g., use case leader) with the Tenant Web Portal during data collection and visualisation process.

Figure 8: Data collection process and KPI assessment using the Tenant Web Portal.

The complete process flow for data collection and processing is shown in Figure 9. The process consists of:

- prior to testing: deployment of the use case in the trial site;
- the experiments are set up in the Tenant Web Portal, consisting of the instantiation of virtualised CAM service backend for the use case;

- the experiments are executed, and the results are either stored locally, or automatically stored in the Tenant Web Portal at the end of each experiment. If the data is stored locally, the use case leader uploads the data manually to the Tenant Web Portal e.g., at the end of the day, after a quality check. Metadata regarding the test is stored (e.g., environmental conditions, specific observations regarding the test);
- after the test session, the data are downloaded from the Tenant Web Portal, and the data are analysed by the partner responsible for the evaluation of the use case;
- the KPIs for the experiments are then fed into the Tenant Web Portal and the composite indicators visualised;
- for each scenario, the aggregated KPIs are calculated based on the KPIs of the different experiments in the Tenant Web Portal.

Figure 9: Process for collecting and processing data.

4.3.2 Data Collection Tools

Data logging in 5G networks can be performed at different OSI-layers, and the results, e.g., the latency, depend on the OSI-layer and the location of the Points of Control and Observation (PCOs). A PCO is a specific point within the system under test, at which either an observation (measurement) is recorded, or traffic is injected. The PCOs are located at the relevant communication interfaces and can be organized in levels. The 5G-MOBIX [13] project defines the following 3 levels for PCOs:

- Level 0, Access level: at this PCO level, information is collected about the radio access network parameters. These measurements are performed with tools provided by the modem or chipset vendor. This PCO allows taking measurement of the cellular network, such as Mobile Network Code (MNC), Mobile Country Code (MCC), signal strength and quality, and the protocol message exchange. It will allow to identify when a handover is taking place;
- Level 1, transport: at IP network/transport layer, using IP connectivity. This level allows evaluating QoS indicators (such as TCP/IP or UDP/IP throughput, UL and DL, one-way delay, packet loss, etc.) and monitoring the traffic received. This level can be implemented at both the UE side and the network side (edge/core);

- Level 2, application level: this is the level where messages are exchanged with the application. Measurements directly integrated in the application, e.g., end-to-end latency, user experienced data rate.

In the 5G-ROUTES project, the following PCOs are used:

- Level 0: measurements at the modems, using software from UE or chipset vendors, e.g., using the APIs provided by the UE or chipset APIs, or special tools such as Keysight Nemo;
- Level 1: software installed at the UEs and at application servers, monitoring the IP traffic. Tools include Qosium, Vedecom KPI Manager, tcpdump and Wireshark;
- Level 2: logging integrated in the application software at the UEs, cloud and at edge applications and enablers developed within 5G-ROUTES project.

Figure 10: Points of Control and Observation (PCOs) in the 5G-ROUTES project

4.3.2.1 Qosium

Qosium, a product of the Finnish company Kaitotek Oy, is a real-time passive network performance measurement solution [32]. It is a product for PCO level 1 and performs real-time QoS and QoE measurements over wireless and wired networks. It allows to monitor and visualise several QoS KPIs (e.g., UL/DL TCP/UDP throughput, network delay, packet error rate etc.) from the sender and receiver viewpoint.

Qosium is used for measuring the traffic flowing between two points in the network path. Qosium makes use of two major components: Qosium Probes and Qosium Scopes. Qosium Probe is a measurement agent which is directly installed in a measurement point, operates in the background in the platform where it is installed as system service, and performs most of the measurement functionalities, like packet capturing and results calculation. Qosium Scope is a measurement controller and collects and visualised the results. [32]

Qosium probes and scopes can be installed in various platforms, permitting to take single or multi-point measurements. The traffic statistics are then collected in CSV format files, allowing to import the data to other platforms such as Microsoft Excel. Typically, values are monitored as averaged values over the user-defined averaging interval.

4.3.2.2 VEDECOM KPI Manager

VEDECOM has developed several modules for monitoring and capturing metrics at the different network level for testing and validating CCAM applications. As illustrated in Figure 11, a KPI manager tools is composed of different component embedded on the 5G OBU for observation of metrics at multiple layers:

- Access Manager is collecting access metrics by querying network information on the 5G modem;

- Network Aggregation Manager is collecting network metrics from the capture of packets on the network interfaces;
- V2X Statistics Manager can provide statistics on the V2X services (cooperative awareness, decentralized event notification, collective perception) by collecting information on exchanged messages.

Figure 11: Overview of KPI manager for on-board units

In addition, these modules can send online measurements on the target indicators to a KPI capture tools via common log data messages. Then, these logs can be stored into a database for further analysis in visualisation.

In the context of 5G-ROUTES, the logs collected through these components should be uploaded either online or offline on the Tenant Web Portal for evaluation of use case performances.

4.3.2.3 Keysight Nemo

Keysight Nemo Outdoor 5G NR Drive Test Solution [34] is a software tool for laptops for wireless network testing.

Keysight Nemo will mainly be used in the project to assess the performance of the control plane. This notably includes measurements related to application state transitions during handover. During handover information can be retrieved including:

- Handover (HO) type (NR handover between cells, NR handover between frequencies, NR handover between bands, NR handover between systems);
- Source/Target cellular system;
- Source/Target band;
- Source/Target channel;
- Source/Target cell id;
- Measurement event (A1-A6, B1-B2) [35];
- Handover duration (With the LTE and NR this defines the handover duration containing handover processing and interrupt time. Time from the handover initiating RRC (Radio Resource Control) signalling message to the successfully completed RACH (Random Access Channel) procedure in the new cell);
- Handover User-plane interruption time (time from the last packet in the old cell to the first packet in the new cell);
- Roaming status (roaming or not roaming).

Nemo runs on a laptop and sets specific requirements to the UE, hence the 5G modem used for the Nemo tests may be different from the 5G modem used for the use case execution.

4.3.2.4 *Tcpdump and Wireshark*

Tcpdump is a network packet analyser and protocol analysis tool. Tcpdump is launched from the command line. It can be used to analyse network traffic by intercepting and displaying packets that are being created or received by the computer it is running on. Tcpdump is hence a powerful tool for resolving network issues. Tcpdump can also capture the whole packages and save them in libpcap format as pcap files.

Wireshark is an open-source network protocol analyser. It is used for network troubleshooting, analysis, software and communications protocol development, and education. Through filters, e.g., for the source or target IP-address, Wireshark saves only the packets of interest. Wireshark can be operated either from a graphical user interface or direct from the command line. Wireshark captured data is stored in the pcapng file format, and also supports the libpcap format, which is used by tcpdump. Wireshark can also be used to analyse the pcap files captured by tcpdump.

In order to get KPIs from pcap files, collected either through tcpdump or Wireshark, scripts are needed to extract the relevant messages, and perform calculations. KPIs which could be calculated include e.g., service disruption time during handover. For the calculation of KPIs related to performance of network, e.g., packet loss or latency, pcap files have to be collected at both the transmitting and receiving nodes, and scripts developed to compare both files.

4.3.2.5 *Getting data from User Equipment*

In order to get information on the network, to which the UE is connected, commands which are specific to the chipset, which is used by UE, are needed. These commands may be integrated in the tools which are mentioned in the previous subsections. If not, collecting the information through AT commands must be integrated with the logging software at application level.

4.4 Performance Indicators

The PIs and KPIs are described in more detail in D1.9 [4] and D1.5 [3]. D1.5 addresses the definition of the tests for network level PIs. The PIs are repeated here to analyse which data is needed to be collected, and to assess the requirements for the data collection process, especially for the technical performance evaluation.

Performance Indicators (PI) can be divided in different categories:

- **Network level PIs.** The different network PIs are described in Section 4.1.1 of D1.5, and include:
 - data rate: peak data rate and user experienced data rate;
 - mobility:
 - intra-cell mobility: maximum angle mobility, maximum doppler mobility;
 - handover time for different scenarios, including inter-operator handover;
 - latency:
 - user plane latency;
 - control plane latency;
 - jitter;
 - connection density (measured using simulation);
 - reliability;
 - network positioning accuracy;
 - network coverage;
 - network availability.

These performance indicators are use case agnostic, and are measured using synthetic data, as described in D1.5, section 4.2. The measurements are performed with dedicated tools, and the PIs will be reported in a specific section of the Tenant Web Portal. In addition to the PIs mentioned in D1.5, the following agnostic PIs will be measured during the use case tests:

Table 4: Agnostic KPIs related to cross-border handover events

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Mobility Interruption Time	The time duration during which a user terminal cannot exchange user plane packets with any base station (or other user terminal) during transitions. This is defined as the time difference between RRC Connection Reconfiguration and New Data Receive messages	Keysight Nemo: Handover Interval (HOI)
Handover preparation time	time between the measurement report by the UE, triggering the handover, until the start of handover execution	Keysight Nemo: time between measurement event information and handover attempt.

- **Use case specific technical PIs** are related to the service level performance for the use cases. The use case specific technical PIs are summarized in Table 5 and described in more detail in section 2.3 of D1.9. Table 5 also identifies the data which need to be measured for the calculation of the PIs. The PIs are generally measured at application level. Special attention is paid to the PIs related to handover and roaming.
- **Business KPIs** are used to assess the ecosystems from a business perspective and are obtained through quantitative and qualitative analyses carried out in WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation Management and Standardisation. The business KPIs are summarized in Table 6 and described in more detail in chapter 5 of D1.9.

Table 5: Use case specific technical PIs and data needed to be measured

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
User experienced data rate	The number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps).	Calculated from application logs during trials.
End-to-end latency	Elapsed time from the moment a data packet is transmitted by the source application to the moment it is received by the destination application instance(s) [23].	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt at the applications, unique message ID Note: a distinction is made between the communication end-to-end latency , which is measured at the application at transmission and receipt of messages, and the user-perceived end-to-end latency , which includes processing of e.g., video.

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Round Trip Time (RTT)	Time it takes for a data packet to be sent to a destination plus the time it takes for an acknowledgment of that packet to be received back at the origin.	Round trip time is an alternative for end-to-end latency if the UE cannot be synchronised. RTT is measured as the time between transmission and response at the same UE, and hence requires automated acknowledgement at the other end.
(Service) reliability	Ratio of messages which is passed successfully (e.g., end-to-end latency within a predefined time limit) between the actors, within the specified range of the service.	Unique Message ID, timestamp of message transmission and receipt at application.
Application Level Handover Success Rate	Applies to scenarios where an active application-level session (e.g., communication between application client at UE/OBU and the Application Server) needs to be transferred from a source to a destination application instance (e.g., located at MEC hosts at the source and destination networks respectively) because of a cross-border mobility event. The KPI describes the ratio of successfully completed application level handovers i.e., where service provisioning is correctly resumed/ continued past the network level handover, from the new application instance [31] within a predefined time limit.	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt at the applications, unique message ID or: connection break time (Qosium) MNC and MCC
Service Interruption Time	Duration during which the application does not exchange information during handover situations (e.g., end-to-end latency within a predefined limit)	Timestamp of message transmission and receipt; application output (e.g., video recording of handover event) or: connection break time (Qosium) MNC and MCC
Service Startup Time after Handover	the time between the end of handover and when the service is fully operational.	From handover completion to request to Assisted service continuity (ASC) until first message from CAM service received (a request to Assisted Service Continuity enabler developed in WP2 is involved)

PI	Definition	Data to be measured during trials
Quality of Experience (QoE)	The overall acceptability of a service, as perceived subjectively by the end user (definition from ITU-T).	The measurement of Quality of Experience depends on the type of service. For audio-visual services the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) is planned to be used. MOS is a widely used indicator for assessing the quality of multimedia signals and can be based either on a subjective basis (MOS-AVQS) or an objective basis (MOS-AVQO). MOS-AVQO represents the MOS score obtained from an algorithmic quality evaluation model, which uses real-time objective metrics that can be obtained from information carried in the audio-visual streams.
Quality of Service	QoS may implies a list of PIs that need to be fulfilled e.g., RTT latency < 10ms AND Reliability>99.999	
Positioning accuracy	Positioning accuracy refers to the closeness of a measured location, to the real location of the device at the time of the measurement (as measured with RTK-GNSS).	UE position compared to more accurate method (if available)
RTK interruption time	Interval during which the UE does not have access to the RTK correction signal when crossing the border [4]	UE position log, s
CAM service instantiation time	time needed for instantiating a CAM service in the CAM Services Platform, from the moment the activation command is sent until the acknowledgement that the CAM service is installed [4].	Integration Fabric log
coverage	percentage of the pilot area which has radio access	UE position, MCC, MNC

Table 6: Business KPIs and data needed to determine the KPI

KPI	Definition	Input data
Maturity/TRL	Technological maturity of a technology	TRL advancement of the 5G ROUTES ecosystems during the field trials.
Obsolescence	The risk that a technology becomes obsolete	Continuous monitoring of the project innovations through the Innovation Registry tool and interviews with the Innovation Manager and Innovation and Commercialisation Board.

KPI	Definition	Input data
BCR	Benefit-Cost Ratio: the ratio between discounted economic benefits and costs.	BCR value based on tangible inputs (costs/benefits), sensitivity analysis (stakeholder level) and qualitative assessment through interviews and questionnaires (stakeholder level)
Penetration rate	The assessment of how much a product is being sold relative to the total estimated market for that product, expressed as a percentage.	Penetration rate (PR) (%) = (number of customers ÷ target market) x 100 For 5G-Routes ecosystems we will need to consider the PR of the 5G equipped vehicle (PRV) and the PR of the 5G infrastructure (PRI). So, the rate of usage of 5G technology over CCAM is calculated by: PRV*PRI The input is not expected from the trials but rather from the thorough market study (T5.1). For the business impact assessment a market penetration of 100% will be considered to the calculations.
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure (infrastructure, vehicles, Hardware/software, etc) required to bring CCAM to wide scale deployment	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
OPEX	Operating Expenses (Human Resources, Insurance, sales, marketing etc.) required for day-to-day operation of a CCAM ecosystem.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
Revenues per year	Revenues produces by the system	Qualitative assessment through interviews and questionnaires (stakeholder level)
Return on Investment (ROI)	Expected ROI (e.g., on 5G telecom infrastructure, automotive and CCAM enabling technologies) from new market opportunities on 5G CCAM.	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
Standardisation	The use of a standardized solution	Interoperability of the 5G Network (low-medium-high) Contribution to related 5G Network and CCAM standards (low-medium-high)
Time to market	The time necessary to offer a commercial system	Stakeholder surveys and interviews centred on commercial solution selected for maritime and terrestrial ecosystems.
Existence of alternative solutions	The risk that other solutions perform better than the proposed one	Continuous monitoring of the project innovations through the Innovation Registry tool and interviews with the Innovation Manager and Innovation and Commercialisation Board.

KPI	Definition	Input data
Opportunities	Opportunities to develop a market around a technology or use case	Thorough market study and SWOT analysis performed in interviews with internal and external stakeholders.
Deployment time	Time to deployment of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems in relation to EC 5G Action Plan [24] and STRIA Roadmap for STRIA Roadmap for Connected and Automated Transport [25].	Deployment Scenarios: Short (2025), Medium (2030), Long (>2030) Relevant trials input: Ecosystem maturity, Technology integration and coverage options (if any) through surveys with the leaders of the two ecosystems.

4.5 Data Collection for Technical Performance Evaluation

The data collected in the project for technical performance evaluation comprises of raw measurements and observations from lab and field trials, and logs exposing the state of the experiments.

To safely manage research data in a broader sense, a Data Management Plan (DMP) has been defined, aiming to make such data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The DMP contains information related to the types of data the project will generate and collect, the standards that will be used to represent the data during the project and how partners might exploit the data resulting from the project. The DMP sets robust management procedures that will protect personal data collected as a result of project activities, as well as client owned data, from unauthorized use or sharing, also supporting GDPR compliance.

Synchronization of the different data sources is critical, especially for measuring latency which is expected to be in the order of milliseconds.

4.5.1 Data Sources

4.5.1.1 Network Related Data

In order to measure network KPIs, probes have to be inserted that intercept the network in proper points at the network. This equipment can monitor the data flow continuously, and store the data needed for calculating the KPIs. The measurement of network KPIs is described in more detail in D1.5 [3].

4.5.1.2 Transport layer data

The traffic between different nodes in the network can be monitored using tools as Qosium (section 0), VEDECOM KPI Manager (section 4.3.2.2). Network traffic at the UE can be monitored using e.g., Keysight Nemo. Network traffic can also be analysed using Wireshark.

Keysight Nemo will be used to collect data for the agnostic KPIs related to cross-border handover events (Table 4). This data will be collected during the first phase of the trials for the terrestrial use cases for use cases I and II.

Qosium will be used for assessing the KPIs in use cases I (UC1.3) and use case II (UC3.1), VEDECOM KPI for use case II.

KPIs which are measured include UL/DL TCP/UDP throughput, latency between two nodes, packet error rate.

4.5.1.3 Use Case Specific Application Level Data

For measurements at application level, the logging of the data will be integrated with the use case applications at the user equipment and at the CAM services.

Vehicle Related Data

Road vehicle data will be collected for the CCAM use case scenarios. The following data will be collected from the vehicles: positioning data, speed, sent and received message timing and size.

For the prototype vehicles, which are used in the CCAM use cases, vehicle data is collected directly from the vehicle electronics and for use case 5.1 from OBUs installed on the vehicles carried by the vessel.

Vehicle data is classified as personal data. Most of the vehicles which are used for the CCAM tests are research vehicles, which are operated by authorized personnel, and data are only logged for the purpose of the tests, hence there are most likely no issues with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). GDPR.

For UC5.1 a vehicle from Vedia and potentially vehicles from a logistic operator may be used. GDPR issues will be addressed using informed consent forms, where the drivers of the vehicles will be informed on the service and on their rights.

Other Equipment Data

For technical performance evaluation, information will be collected from other 5G-nodes, such as infrastructure and IoT sensors connected to the 5G-network, end user devices (including consumer devices) and application servers.

Each device will have a unique identifier (stationID), which consists of a prefix assigned to the partner owning the device, e.g., 35831 for VTT, and a number assigned by the partner.

The following data has to be stored for all devices:

- **Messages: message type** (e.g., CAM, CPM...), **timestamp** included in the V2X message (or e.g., in unix epoch of receipt/transmission of message generation), **station ID** of the sender, **size**;
- **Position: latitude, longitude, speed**, heading, positioning method, accuracy, timestamp of correction data;
- **Vehicle Dynamics:** (for vehicle use cases): yaw rate, acceleration (lateral, longitudinal), speed wheel distance, brake status, manual/automated mode;
- **Application Status:** timestamp, status code;
 - the execution of a use case can be seen as a state machine (e.g., no obstacles > obstacle detection > critical obstacle detection > manoeuvre activation > manoeuvre completion)
- Synchronisation statistics, generated e.g., from chrony, to be able to assess that time synchronisation has worked;
- RTT or ping information (to e.g., MQTT broker), as backup in case of loss of synchronisation.

In case the User Equipment or the IoT sensor has only limited processing capabilities, not all the desired information may be possible to be logged. Synchronisation using Network Time Protocol (NTP) or other technologies may not always be possible.

Data collected by nomadic devices used by test users will be anonymized, and it will be assured that the test user cannot be identified from the data logged on the service.

Test Metadata

For each experiment, metadata related to the experiment will be collected. This data includes factors which may affect the analysis of the results. Among others, the following data will be collected for controlled tests:

- experiment identifier: use case identifier, test scenario identifier, repetition identifier

- For each use case, a set of test scenarios are identified, corresponding to different variations of the use case (e.g., vehicle speed, presence of road users) and/or different variations of the network;
- environmental conditions: temperature, weather conditions (cloudy, sunny, rain, fog...) and road weather (dry, wet, ice, snow...);
- network configuration;
- events influencing the test execution:
 - deviations from the storyboard, e.g., a pedestrian or vehicle deviated from the agreed trajectory;
 - unexpected traffic events, e.g., additional road users or objects on the track;
 - safety events: the safety driver had to take manual control during automated driving.

Overview of Data Collected for the Different Use Cases

Table 7 gives an overview of the devices, on which data will be collected during evaluation.

Table 7: Overview of devices in 5G-ROUTES where data at application level will be logged

Use Case	Vehicle	other devices	servers and enablers
I	✓		V2X broker
II	✓	Traffic light controller, cameras, RSU	V2X broker
4.1	-	User smart device	Users game server, Real-time game server.
4.2	-	Broadcast virtual set, graphics station	-
5.1	OBU	RSU, IoT devices	backend
5.2	OBU	camera on OBU	cloud server

4.5.1.4 Collecting Metrics from Enablers

In addition to the data collected from the devices used in the use cases, data has to be collected from the enablers. The enablers will log metrics on their behaviour and transmit this information to the Tenant Web Portal. Data should at least be stored at each enabler regarding:

- state of changes of devices, including accurate time stamp and the old and new state;
- messages exchanged, including sender, (receiver), timestamp and topic. This requirement may have to be reviewed if it causes too much storage and/or the data is not used in further assessments.

The data will be downloaded by the use case leaders for the assessment of the data for the use case.

4.5.2 Data Storage Formats

Raw measurements with related parameters, such as timestamps, etc., are stored in plain text format, such as comma separated values (CSV). The raw measurements are pre-processed at the time of data-collection to remove any personally identifiable information, such as IP address, leaving only anonymous and unique machine identifiers along with other parameters related to computations. Logs that contain the history of the state of various processing elements are also stored in plain text format.

The data, which have been used for evaluation, will be uploaded to the Tenant Web Portal, as described in section 4.3.1, and at the end of the project transferred to Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories.

In order to distinct between the different files, the following naming is suggested:

`<log_item>_<log_stationid>_<experimentID>.<filetype>`

Where:

- **log_item**: Identifies the type of log_item contained in the file. Examples are: “Message”, “Position”, “VehicleDynamics”, “Perception” and “ApplicationEvent”;
- **log_stationid**: StationID of the device generating the logging;
- **experimentID**: the ID of the experiment, received from the Tenant Web Portal. If no experiment ID is received, the timestamp in either Unix epoch or YYYYMMDD'T'HHmmss format is used. The same identifier should be used for all files, collected from different devices, and belonging to the same experiment;
- **filetype**: Standard file type of the log file, e.g., “csv”. The first row contains the names of the parameters to be stored.

For each logged row, the following data has to be included:

- log_stationID: the log station that has sent or transmitted the data;
- log_timestamp: timestamp at which the log application logs the item, corresponding to unix epoch time.

4.5.3 Data Quality Requirements

In order to be useful for evaluation, the quality of the data has to be assured. This includes the following aspects:

- Timing synchronization. As the latency PI targets are in the order of 10 ms, the time in the different 5G-nodes must be synchronised in order to be able to measure latency. A high accuracy is required due to the low expected latencies; hence target should be to have accuracy in the 1 ms range. The following techniques can be used for time synchronisation:
 - The preferred technique is the use of PTP (Precision Time Protocol);
 - GNSS time reference for the 5G nodes. Use of the PPS (Pulse per Second) signal allows for synchronisation with other sensors;
 - NTP (Network Time Protocol) or Chrony. NTP typically provides a precision in the order of a millisecond.
- Sanity check of all variables, i.e., that the variables are within the expected range (e.g., locations near the actual site, speeds in normal range).
- All mandatory data is stored. Mandatory data for exchanged messages includes:
 - unique reference number for the message, so that a single message can be traced along its delivery path;
 - logging timestamp of the message.
- The data is logged in the agreed format. Data are stored in csv files. The different variables are in the agreed units and in the agreed format, e.g., timestamp represented as Unix epoch time, and speeds in km/h.
- The values of the logged data are within the expected range, e.g., GNSS-data are not zero.
- When performing measurements at application level at the UE, it should be assured that there are no other applications or functions which may affect the timing of the receipt or transmission of the messages.

During border crossing, the service may be disrupted for a time. A set of KPIs has been identified for the measurement of service interruption. During the service interruption period, temporary abnormal values for the metrics such as for metrics such as latency and data rate, can be measured. In addition, the measured values at both sides of the border can be different, due to e.g., different configuration of the networks or longer data transmission paths. The measurements for cross-border tests may have to be split in several parts: connection to network A, handover/service disruption, connection to network B, and the metrics to be calculated for each part separately based on the measurement logs containing these events.

Data regarding the connection to network and the 5G-ROUTES enablers, used by the use case, should be collected to assess the behaviour of the use case on the border and the impact of the enablers of the handover process.

4.5.4 Calculation of Performance Indicators from Measured Values

For each experiment, a set of data is obtained consisting of:

- series of measured values, such as message transmission/receival timestamps, message size, position, (message payload information), network data;
- event data, e.g., device state change, application decisions.

For time series of numerical values, a number of statistical metrics can be obtained, such as:

- median;
- 95% percentile (or any other percentile);
- average;
- minimum, maximum;
- standard deviation;
- confidence interval.

For a test scenario, the tests will be repeated under the same conditions for improved statistical relevance. The amount of experiments (repetitions) for each scenario should preferably be repeated 10 times.

After collection of the data, a quality check is performed, and the different Performance Indicators are calculated for the different experiments. Selected PIs, which are selected as being important for the evaluation of the use case, are then entered as PI in the Tenant Web Portal.

The values of the PIs for different experiments of a specific scenario are then compared, to check if they can be combined, or if there is a significant difference caused by e.g., vehicle speed, environmental conditions or the local configuration of the network, or due to an abnormal event during the experiment execution. In case there is a significant difference between the PIs of different experiments, the experiment may be assessed as belonging to a new scenario.

The PIs, obtained for the separate experiments, must be aggregated to a PI for the scenario. When PIs are calculated from time series, care has to be taken that the calculated aggregated values have a sound mathematical basis. Initially, the aggregated value for the scenario is calculated in the Tenant Web as the average of the different experiments.

Composite indicators, as defined in D1.9, are then calculated for the scenario and visualised.

4.6 End-User Involvement and End-User Data

4.6.1 End-User Participation in Testing

The main purpose of the evaluation in 5G-ROUTES is to assess the impact of 5G and the 5G-ROUTES solutions on the services. In order to be able to distinct the impact of R16 to earlier releases, subjective opinions of test users may not result in reliable results, especially for the cross-border effects.

For tests performed at the cross-border, the recruitment of test users is challenging. For the road use cases, local partners need to be involved for recruitment of the users, and translation of the interviews and the results. In addition, for tests with autonomous vehicles is challenging, as there may be ethical/liability requirements which prevent taking passengers on board. For the ferry cases, as passengers on board have to be asked to participate and the time needed for the traditional user interaction process (briefing, pre-questionnaire, test, post-questionnaire) may not suit many passengers.

Hence, the type of end-users involved in the evaluation, depend on the use case and the possibility to recruit “normal” persons from outside the consortium. Currently, only personnel from the consortium partners are planned as test users, and only for assessing the technical performance.

4.6.2 Collection of Data for Business Validation

4.6.2.1 *Customer Validation and Solution Alignment Surveys and Interviews*

The Customer Validation phase requires detailed examination of the key personas in each ecosystem and the likely benefit that they expect to gain from eventual large-scale uptake of the proposed scenario.

This data will be gathered primarily from the stakeholders of the two ecosystems in a Survey format with further interviews where necessary to clarify specific details. Figure 12, Figure 13 and Figure 14 illustrate the questionnaire to be used for the Customer Validation process. Findings will be reported in D5.2.

Business Context and Problem Definition

Background																																
<p><i>Please provide a textual description of the business process and context surrounding the UC.</i></p> <p><i>What is the general context of the UC? (describe situation in which the UC arises; be specific; focus on the Business/commercial side rather than technical)</i></p> <p><i>Under what circumstances does the UC arise?</i></p> <p><i>How often?</i></p> <p><i>Other information?</i></p>																																
Describe the Personas																																
<p><i>Please describe ALL personas who are directly involved in YOUR specific UC;</i></p> <p><i>Please be as specific and detailed as possible about exactly what each persona does.</i></p> <p>Category: Users (e.g. Drivers, vehicle owners, Passengers, Pedestrians, ...)</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Name</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Role</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Category: Telecom (i.e. manufacturers, operators)</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Name</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Role</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Category: Transport (i.e. rail, maritime or automotive manufacturers, rail, maritime or automotive operators)</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Name</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Role</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Category: Service providers (i.e. ITS service providers, Network service providers, Infotainment service providers, Consultants/Business innovators)</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Name</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Persona Role</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Category: Others (i.e. Research, Public Authorities, Standardisation Network/Authorities, other (please indicate))</p>	Persona Name	Persona Role							Persona Name	Persona Role							Persona Name	Persona Role							Persona Name	Persona Role						
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Figure 12: Customer Validation Survey used in 5G-ROUTES: Business Context and Problem Definition

Describe the Problem									
<i>Describe in detail the problems that each persona/stakeholder currently experience (AS-IS today <u>before 5G</u>)</i>									
<p>Personas (who exactly?) experience this problem (what exactly?) when doing this task (when does it occur?) OR</p> <p>Personas (who exactly?) experience this problem (what exactly?) because of this constraint or limitation (when does it occur?)</p>									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>End user Persona</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Problem</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Task / Constraint</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		End user Persona		<i>Problem</i>		<i>Task / Constraint</i>		<i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i>	
End user Persona									
<i>Problem</i>									
<i>Task / Constraint</i>									
<i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i>									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Application Provider Persona</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Problem</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Task / Constraint</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Application Provider Persona		<i>Problem</i>		<i>Task / Constraint</i>		<i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i>	
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<i>Problem</i>									
<i>Task / Constraint</i>									
<i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i>									
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Other Personas</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Problem</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Task / Constraint</i></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		Other Personas		<i>Problem</i>		<i>Task / Constraint</i>		<i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i>	
Other Personas									
<i>Problem</i>									
<i>Task / Constraint</i>									
<i>How is it addressed now? (Pre-5G)</i>									

Figure 13: Customer Validation Survey used in 5G-ROUTES: Problem Description

Describe the Expected Benefit	
<i>Describe the benefit that each persona hopes to achieve from the UC (after 5G is implemented). Please try to be specific on the benefits that may apply .. Cost? Time? Agility? Safety? Security?</i>	
End user personas	
Describe benefit	
Specific benefit	<i>Quantify the potential benefit</i>
Cost reduction?	
Revenue Increase?	
Time saved?	
Faster Time-to-Market?	
Safety?	
Security?	
Accessibility?	
Persona experience?	
Other...	
Application Provider Personas	
Describe benefit	
Specific benefit	<i>Quantify the potential benefit</i>
Cost reduction?	
Revenue Increase?	
Time saved?	
Faster Time-to-Market?	
Safety?	
Security?	
Accessibility?	
Persona experience?	
Other...	
Other Personas	
Describe benefit	
Specific benefit	<i>Quantify the potential benefit</i>
Cost reduction?	
Revenue Increase?	
Time saved?	
Faster Time-to-Market?	
Safety?	
Security?	
Accessibility?	
Persona experience?	
Other...	

Figure 14: Customer Validation Survey used in 5G-ROUTES: Expected Benefit

Solution Alignment takes the learnings from Customer Validation, applies them to the potential products from the project to see which have the best fit and asks two questions:

- (i) What products could go to market?
- (ii) Which partners are the best to lead on developing the business plan and commercialization?

For 5G-ROUTES, the goal is to assess the two ecosystems’ solutions. A lead commercial partner will be chosen for each market service based on the likely customer journey and the commercial and technical capacity and expertise in each field of activity. The survey illustrated in Figure 15 will be filled in during an interview with the commercial leader to look more into the details of the exploitation potential foreseen by each partner. Findings of this process will be reported in D5.2.

Commercial Exploitation Potential

Please provide your ideas on the outputs your business hopes to commercialise from 5G-ROUTES. Be as explicit as possible in defining the potential outputs and setting a vision for the offering that your company could create.

+
<p>What? Please describe the Product(s) and/or Service(s) that you believe you could commercialise from this project</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What does the product(s) or service(s) do for a customer? What problem does it address? 2. How would it fit into your current business? Do you already provide a related product/service, or would this be something completely new for your business? 3. How might the product/service be delivered? Is it hardware? Software? Software- As-A-service, A/ Gaming Device? Consultancy/advisory service? Etc. etc.
□
<p>Who? Please describe the customer(s) who would pay for the product or service that you envisage</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can you describe who you believe is the customer(s) for the product/service? (examples: Users (e.g. Drivers, vehicle owners, Passengers, Pedestrians, ..), Telecom (i.e. manufacturers, operators), Transport (i.e. rail, maritime or automotive manufacturers, rail, maritime or automotive operators), Service providers (i.e. ITS service providers, Network service providers, Infotainment service providers, Consultants/Business innovators), Others (i.e. Research, Public Authorities, Standardisation Network/Authorities, other (please indicate)) 2. Top 3 specific customer segments who will care the most about your product? And Why?
<p>Why? Why would customers choose your (future) offering above other approaches? What do you think will make it special?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is special about your offering? What is “game-changing” from other products and/or services? 2. Can you describe the market opportunity for your company? (e.g. we could replace x% of all current products in area-y within 5 years; we could attract 5% of all current users of y within 10 years, etc.).

Figure 15: Solution Alignment Survey used in 5G-ROUTES

4.6.2.2 Workshops

Stakeholder workshops will act as a major data collection tool for the implementation of the MAMCA methodology. The aims of those workshops are twofold:

- To identify and weight the business criteria (internal stakeholder rating);

- To rank the value propositions against the weighted criteria and against each other (resulting to max 2 value propositions to be processed in the CBA).

To facilitate the latter, more complex process, stakeholders will be presented with the business context (5G ROUTES ecosystems), including a real (or video) demonstration where feasible, to have a better understanding of the business potential. This knowledge will give them the right insight to follow the MAMCA ranking of the proposed value propositions and rate them against the identified business criteria.

One workshop is planned for the business criteria identification and rating (Step 3 of MAMCA method depicted in Figure 6), which will be on a horizontal basis (use case independent but relevant to the business potential of 5G as enabler of CCAM), and at the next phase, one workshop per each business ecosystem (maritime and terrestrial) that will select the most promising value propositions and the related business criteria where the CBA should focus on (Step 5 of MAMCA method).

4.6.2.3 Interviews

Stakeholder interviews will support the in-depth business analysis and CBA.

After each stakeholder ecosystem is evaluated through the two MAMCA workshops, the interviews plan to assess the clear business interest in the 5G-ROUTES solutions or otherwise a significant role in an emerging business ecosystem. Such interviews will be restricted to 1-2 identified business investor(s)/leader(s) per each 5G-ROUTES defined business ecosystem.

The value propositions discussed in the interviews will be selected based on a role and interest of an interviewee along with the results of the previous data collection tools. A thorough SWOT analysis will be performed during the interview and corrections to the financial and economic models will be taken into consideration.

Finally, the opportunities for exploitation of 5G-ROUTES business values will be discussed and scaled-up, creating new markets beyond the limits of 5G-ROUTES ecosystems.

5 Test Plan

This chapter discusses test plan issues at a general level. The test plan will be generated before the start of the test session, where information for the evaluation is collected in WP4. The test scenarios will be described in more detail in D4.1. The test plan has two purposes:

- it is a tool to guarantee the success of the trials, i.e., that the trials are performed without problems, and that the tests generate high quality data for evaluation;
- it is a reference document for external evaluators, to explain what is happening, including all aspects which may have an impact on the interpretation of the result, e.g., potential bias if the environment is not completely corresponding to a real traffic environment.

The test plan must address the following issues:

- description of the use case to be tested;
- overview of the test cases to be performed;
- planning of the test events;
- organisation of the test events.

5.1 Use Case Description and Test Cases

For the evaluation, a clear description of the use case is required. This description can be used to describe to the stakeholders, test users, evaluation team and other actors how the use case is performed, and what the role of each actor and participant in the use case is.

The test plan should also include an extensive list of all the scenarios and test cases which are planned to be tested, i.e., the variations in network configuration, road users and test parameters.

Elements of the use case description are:

- description of the actors involved in the test and their roles;
- storyboard, describing the consecutive phases of the use cases (and potential alternatives). Graphs with e.g., the position and movements of all actors are beneficial;
- description of the information flow between the different components, including sequence diagram. Description of the messages which are exchanged, including the standards or specification in use. Description of the security solution in place (e.g., TLS), including details on how to receive the required certificates;
- description of the network infrastructure, vehicles and other sensors and devices used in the test. Description of the potential different configurations of the communication network. Description of the 5G-ROUTES enablers which are implemented in the network.

Scenarios and Test cases

For the use cases, different scenarios have been defined in D1.9 [4]. In this phase, the test cases to test the different scenarios will be detailed. This includes:

- description of the test route;
- description of the test scenarios of the use case and the potential variations:
 - description in potential network variations and enabler configurations to be tested;
 - description of the potential variations in the scenario, e.g., number of road users involved or variations in the behaviour of road users;

- determining the parameters for performing the tests, e.g., target vehicle speed and initial vehicle distance;
- determination of the number of test repetitions or sample size, to guarantee statistical relevant results:
 - for technical tests: each scenario should ideally be repeated 10 times under identical circumstances in order to get statistical relevant results;
 - in case end users are involved, the target users and their properties (gender and age distribution, experience...). A minimum of 30 test users is advised to achieve statistical significance.

5.2 Test Preparation

During this period, after having determined the scenarios and the test cases to be tested, the following categories must be addressed:

- administrative and ethical issues: assuring that all permits are in place, and ethical issues are addressed;
- system preparation: assuring that all tools are in place for data collection;
- test logistics.

5.2.1 Administrative and Ethical Issues

This section deals with administrative issues to be handled well in advance, such as assuring that all permits are in place, and with ethical issues, related to ensuring the safety of all test participants and the privacy of involved road and test users.

The following issues have to be addressed:

- applying for and acquiring the permits needed for performing out the tests at the test site;
 - for testing of automated driving on public roads, specific registration procedures are needed. If the roads are closed for other traffic, these registration procedures are not needed. Hence, in order to perform automated driving tests, the roads must be closed for other public traffic, or the tests have to be performed at a closed site;
 - in case the tests are performed on public roads, special provisions may be required by local or national authorities to ensure the safety of all road users. This may include specific road (work) permits and putting traffic signs or trailers in place.
- ensuring the safety of test participant and all road users:
 - in case the use case addresses safety critical traffic situations, it must be ensured that no actual damage to persons or vehicles will occur. Automated vehicles require a safety driver which can take control at each moment and override the automated actions. It also may require limiting the speed of the manoeuvre, so that the safety driver has sufficient time to react;
 - in case tests are performed on public road: the actions, needed to inform the public about the test have to be discussed with local authorities. If a road or a section of the road is temporary close, safety equipment to guide the public, such as road guiding trailers, may have to be put in place. Dependent on local regulations, persons, who have the required permits, must be hired to guide traffic.
- privacy related issues: assuring that all GDPR issues are addressed, including assessment whether a DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) is needed.
- potential labour related issues, e.g., in case tests are performed at night.

5.2.2 System Preparation

The use cases to be demonstrated must be prepared for the trials. The use case developers have to assure that all data collection measures are in place, and that data of high quality can be collected. This includes e.g., assuring that, if needed, RTK correction data is available.

The use cases may require detailed information on the road network and/or telecommunication network topology. It has to be assured that the use cases have the required information.

5.2.3 Logistic Issues

Organising CCAM tests is a resource intensive task, especially if it involves different vehicles of different partners and different telecom providers, and several use cases may be tested in parallel. Hence, during the same testing period, several use cases will have to work together, and the different testing activities must be coordinated, especially if different use cases have different demands regarding the 5G network configuration. Tests take generally several days, involving at least one preparation day to assure that everything is working. Provisions have to be taken that the persons participating in the tests can work efficiently and safely. The following aspects have to be addressed:

- issues related to the test site/facility:
 - contact persons at site/facility, which are responsible for, respectively, the interaction between researchers and facility managers/local authorities and the interaction between the researchers and on-site technicians. Contact persons for technical issues, e.g., related to 5G-networks or SIM cards. This also including briefing of the researchers.
 - access to the test site/facilities:
 - timing: during which days and time of the day the test facilities are available;
 - security related issues: are access permits required, is free movement within the test site facility allowed;
 - visitors to the tests: can visitors (e.g., reviewers, local authorities, dissemination public) be invited to the tests, and which specific procedures for access control to the facility?
 - services needed for the test:
 - access to electric power, also for charging electric vehicles,
 - local services:
 - control room or space (e.g., heated tent), which can be used by the researchers for coordination of the test activities and for e.g., solving software problems or verifying test results. Researchers should not be forced to work outside in the cold, heat or rain...
 - potentially room which can be used for dissemination: in case there are external experts (e.g., reviewers, invited authorities...) coming to see the trials, there should be a possibility for giving short presentations;
 - in case the test involves external test users, location where briefing and interviews will take place;
 - availability of catering;
 - parking and storage related issues: there should be a location where test equipment can be securely stored in between testing days.
 - in case the facility shared with other actors (either internally in the project – with other use cases, or externally to the project), the interaction between the different actors should be clear.

- schedule:
 - time should be foreseen for: setting up equipment and pre-test; time for performing tests; time for dismantling and debriefing. In case different use cases are being tested in the same period in the same location, a more detailed timing of testing of the different use cases is needed.
 - for ferry:
 - the interaction between use case testing and the movement of ferry should be clear, e.g., if there any specific processes at the terminals (i.e., in between the ferry is at the end destination and returns to the start). Ferry schedule should be provided, especially the timing of border crossings (i.e., timing that handover can be tested).

6 Use Case Specific Aspects

6.1 Terrestrial Ecosystem

6.1.1 I. See-Through Platooning

1. Use case

The objective of the use is to demonstrate how CAM services, deployed in the available points of presence by the CAM Services Platform, which is developed in 5G-ROUTES, can be used to support drivers when moving across borders. Demonstrated support functions are platooning for automated vehicles supported by see-through video transmission as well as remote support to the drivers.

In the platooning sub use-case (UC1.1), the objective is to implement a system for automated vehicles to dynamically form a platoon with harmonized speeds, following a piloting vehicle. By using a combination of sensors and communication, the aim is to reduce inter-vehicular distances to a safe minimum while also supporting border crossing and providing a radar-based fallback mechanism.

During the platoon, vehicles can perform automated lane change manoeuvres (UC1.2), while also taking into account the intentions of other vehicles. By using a combination of sensors and communication, movements of the vehicles are coordinated in a way that reduces unnecessary changes in speed and keeps the drivers safe, while also supporting border crossing scenarios.

The see-through capability (UC1.3) gives the (safety) driver of a vehicle in a platoon a view of the traffic situation in front of the leading vehicle. The main objective of this sub-use case is to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness during platooning and for safe automated manoeuvres. The objective is to support the driver to make decisions when there is a need to leave the platoon.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The main cross-border issue is to guarantee service continuity and low latency V2X message transmission for the entire duration of the platoon while the vehicles are crossing the border, as well as to provide continuous video transmission between the vehicle in front and the following vehicles.

The use case makes use of the video proxy CAM service for transmission of the video, which is integrated with the CAM Services Platform. The solution also makes use of the platoon management service, which is deployed on the cloud.

In a local breakout roaming configuration, the video proxy CAM service must be deployed on the visiting network to support the vehicles crossing the border. The use of slicing is beneficial in guaranteeing low latency for the V2X messages needed for the execution of the use case (e.g., vehicle odometry, status information) and for the distribution of the video

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity for the service, respectively.
- The 5G-ROUTES enablers allow to instantiate the virtualise CAM services in the visiting network in time to guarantee seamless service continuity (Local Breakout configuration).

- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and throughput.
- High positioning accuracy for supporting automated driving is available at both sides of the border.
- Different live video sources streamed on the same network do not collide or overload the network bandwidth capacity.

4. Use case scenarios

The following evaluation tests are planned:

- First set of trials: transmission of video and of V2X between 2 UEs. The second UE is either static or in the same vehicle.
- Second set of trials: execution of the use case scenario for 2 or 3 vehicles crossing the border:
 - platoon consisting of 2 or 3 vehicles crossing the border (UC1.1)
 - platoon of 2 vehicles performing lane change manoeuvre in the border area (UC1.2)
 - video transmission between 2 vehicles following each other across the border (UC1.3).
 - demonstration of use case scenario with 3 vehicles and video transmission

The use of slicing will be evaluated, with one slice for the V2X traffic and one slice for the video transfer.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- EDI: develop cooperative driving-related applications and services (UC1.1, UC1.2), supply two electric vehicles (equipped with LIDAR, radar, camera, GNSS-RTK, 5G communication system, drive-by-wire system and on-board computer) capable of automated driving, that can also host VTT's video streaming application if needed.
- VTT: responsible for video streaming application development (UC1.3), and for the OBU which takes care of video transmission, streaming and reception (1 OBU with camera, 1 OBU with display).
- TTU and Ericsson: provide network infrastructure.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials for platooning (UC1.1 and UC1.2) are mainly performed on the Biķernieki racetrack, where a simulated border-crossing environment is provided. Small-scale tests are also done in EDI premises, where a small intersection and roads with lane-markings are available in addition to a commercial 5G network.

Lab trials for the video transmission (UC1.3) are performed in Finland in both VTT's 5GTN network in Otaniemi, and in the commercial 5G networks. Additional lab trials are performed in conjunction with CTC lab to test the integration of UC1.3 with the required enablers of the CAM Services Platform.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

For testing automated driving: Closed road, controllable environment.

8. Location for field trials

The large-scale trials are planned to be performed on the Biķernieki racetrack.

9. Logging of data and logging process

For platooning and lane change (UC1.1, UC1.2): Logging utilizing ROS based ecosystem, i.e., using rosbag files with synchronized data in addition to Wireshark for network measurements.

For video transmission, data will be collected from the OBUs (which will be installed in EDI/LMT vehicles) and from VTT vehicle, and from the video proxy, using Qosium. For the first set of trials, Keysight Nemo will be used for analysis of handover events.

Chrony or PTP (Precision Time Protocol) is used to synchronize applications.

The data, collected during trial experiments, will be exported to the Tenant Web tools using the provided API.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

The trials do not include end-user involvement. Local stakeholders will provide their feedback during the trials.

6.1.2 II. Sharing Perception and Road Hazard at the Border for Connected and Automated Driving

1. Use case

This use case consists of different functionalities, which involve CAM services which are disseminating data packets towards road users (vehicles, roadworkers...) through the V2X Message Routing enabler to ensure safety and continuity of traffic related information during border crossing. A common requirement is hence that the service continuity has to be assured when crossing borders to maintain a high level of availability in the automated driving functionalities by ensuring that a CAV can quickly respond to any unlikely event. As vehicles are driving in mixed conditions, i.e., where vehicles from both sides of the countries are sharing the same driving environment, similar information must be disseminated on both sides.

The use case consists of different the following services:

- 1) **Sensor information sharing for situational awareness** (UC3.1)
- 2) **Infrastructure assisted advanced driving** (based on UC2.1).
- 3) **Collision warning with mobile roadwork operation**(based on UC3.3)

In the **Infrastructure assisted advanced driving** service, 5G networks and road infrastructure technologies are used to improve road users' safety and traffic efficiency in a cross-border environment. Based on ETSI specifications, the periodic broadcast of CPM, CAM, SPATEM, MAPEM messages supports connected and automated vehicles (CAV) while driving across the border. The service created through the messages exchange consider the attributes of vehicles, road infrastructure and detected objects.

In the **sensor information sharing** service, processed sensor data is exchanged among vehicles, Road Site Units (RSU), road user UEs and V2X application servers, in order to achieve cooperative situation awareness. Vehicles use their own sensors (e.g., HD camera, LIDAR), and sensor information from other vehicles, to perceive the environment (e.g., come up with 3D model of world around it) and safely performs automated manoeuvres.

In **collision warning with mobile roadwork operation**, safety related information where roadwork agents are in intervention, e.g., for maintenance of the road, is shared. In such condition, a vehicle from a road operator is slowly moving to delimit the roadwork area and warn other users of the dangerous situations. Connected

and automated vehicles approaching from the other side of the border need to be informed and continuously updated as the situation changes.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The different use cases have the following common challenges:

- The services offered to the vehicle users (mobile roadwork warning, infrastructure perception) should be available on both sides of the border thanks to the V2X Message Broker and accessible when crossing the border without disruption.
- The use cases using CAM services (e.g., mobile roadwork warning, infrastructure perception), should be able to disseminate information to both sides of the border.
- Slicing allows to reserve resources for V2X services, guaranteeing low latency for time critical functionalities, also when crossing borders.
- Availability of 5G positioning enhancing at both sides of the border, assuring sufficiently good accuracy for automated driving.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service.
- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and reliability for different types of user equipment (vehicle OBUs, road agent devices, roadside infrastructure router).
- High positioning accuracy for supporting automated driving is available at both sides of the borders.

4. Use case scenarios

The following trials are planned:

- First set of trials: transmission of V2X messages between 2 UEs.
- Second set of trials: The objective of this scenario is to assess the performance of 5G and the CAM Services Platform for informing vehicles on safety critical situations and to assist automated driven vehicles.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

Partners and Roles

- SWARCO: main responsible for the Infrastructure-assisted advanced driving service, and will provide the applications
- VTT is responsible for application development for sensor sharing service, and the OBUs for sensor sharing (1 OBU with camera and LIDAR), vehicle for automated manoeuvre.
- VEDECOM: Supply vehicles equipped with on-board units and develop roadwork warning of cooperative and automated driving service.
- CERTH: Supply 5G devices and C-ITS applications which can be installed in vehicles (e.g., CAV or road operator vehicle). One portable device can be carried by a roadworker or easily installed in a test vehicle.
- ERICSSON: 5G Infrastructure provider and developer of CAM infrastructure;

- TTU: CCAM infrastructure developer;
- Cities: providing the required infrastructure and authorizations for the intelligent infrastructure.

Infrastructure for Valka-Valga intersections:

- 2 Controllers SWARCO Tech;
- 6 Combia traffic lights;
- 10 Beamer devices;
- 2 Roadside Units;
- 4 cameras (i.e., 2 in each intersection);
- 2 Swarm analytic devices with AI capabilities;
- 2 Routers 5G/4G;
- Tablet or a smartphone.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials take place near the facilities of the use case developers: for roadworks warning in Versailles, for perception sharing in Tampere.

Tests for the infrastructure-assisted advanced driving are performed in TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn).

Additional lab trials may be performed in conjunction with CTC lab to test the integration of the virtualised CAM Service Backend of these use cases with the required enablers of the CAM Services Platform

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

5G network to enable the service continuity considering the cross-border scenario

Cities/Road authorities:

- contacts;
- authorization procedures and guidelines;
- installation activities authorization;
- the configuration of the actual traffic light plan or an updated plan.

Documentation required:

- signal timing sheet;
- intersection electrical drawings;
- installation policies and procedures (according to local authorities).

Roads with accident prone areas (e.g., blind spots, intersections) are expected to highlight the potential benefits of use case services.

When performing automated driving manoeuvres, the roads should be closed for other traffic

8. Location for field trials

E264 motorway between Estonia and Latvia borders. In specific, crossing the cities of Valka and Valga.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Data will be collected from the OBUs and from the vehicles from VTT and VEDECOM and from the CERTH devices, and from the V2X Message Routing enabler, according to the formats described in D2.7. Data of the intelligent infrastructure will be logged.

Chrony or PTP is used to synchronise clocks between different devices.

The data collected during trial test runs experiments will be exported to the Tenant Web tools using the provided API.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

Data gathering: questionnaires to the external stakeholder participants.

The main stakeholders are the project partners, the city/road authorities and the road users.

6.1.3 UC4.1 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go

1. Use case

The main objective of the use case is to allow groups of users to play Augmented Reality (AR) video games while on-route, and to provide a fluid and identical AR scene status to all participants without the need to apply dead reckoning techniques that always lend to unfair game situations for users with higher latency connections.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

Guarantee low-latency data transmission and service continuity even when users are crossing the border. The solution uses a server place in a point of presence in the edge to deploy the game server to ensure low latency communication and ensure dissemination of messages. When the players are approaching the border the game service is duplicated in the edge of the visiting country and synchronised with the service running in the first country.

The use of slicing is beneficial in guaranteeing low latency data transmission, needed for real-time game update, avoid lag and user synchronization.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service, respectively;
 - real-time game service can be successfully deployed, instantiated and synchronised on the visiting country on edge servers;
 - users' game information can be exchanged between the servers in an interoperable way, also across borders;
 - the end-to-end latency is within the target;
 - slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and reliability for smart devices.
-

4. Use case scenarios

The following field trials are planned:

- First set of trials: transmission of gaming data between game server and a single UE (smart phone or tablet) crossing the border
- Second set of trials:
 - Multi-user gaming for users in vehicles crossing the border (for terrestrial)
 - Multi-user gaming for users in a ferry

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

PARTNERS INVOLVED:

- BRAINSTORM: Leader of the use case. Provides AR application and related containerized gaming server;
- ATOS: Validate the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment;
- TTU, Ericsson: provide network environment

EQUIPMENT:

- **Game servers:** deployed on edge computer near the base stations, in charge of receiving all users' interactions, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and finally updating all remote devices accordingly.
- **User smart devices:** Android smart phone or tablet including a camera will display the game status overlaid on the camera capture, depending on where the player is pointing the device, and the last game update from the game server. 5G infrastructure compatible.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trial's location : CTTC – Barcelona. In addition to those tests explained above, CTTC lab will also support trials related to the integration of UC4.1 with the required enablers of CAM Services Platform.

The tests will be focused on the application compatibility and evaluating the 5G network capabilities before the field trials, specifically measure the network latency and how it affects the user QoE.

The data will be captured by the mobile device in order to check the network expected performance.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- Predefined known routes in case the AR contents are decided to be linked to the real world;
- edge node servers on the base stations to assure low latency;
- at least 5 minutes route duration for optimal testing.

8. Location for field trials

- terrestrial tests: Estonia/Latvia border in Valga;
- maritime tests: ferry between Tallinn-Helsinki.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Data logged by the smartphones:

- timestamp for each interaction with the game server;
- Clients KPIs (Full-loop latency, Jitter, Messages in per second, Data in throughput, Data out throughput, Output message size, Input message size) logs.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

Stakeholders:

- Technological institute for children's products & leisure (AIJU) – technological centre specialized in physical toys and interactive play experiences.

User involvement:

- Technological institute for children's products & leisure (AIJU): as it is not possible to get personnel from AIJU in the lab and to the field trial, the results will be presented to them in the way of documentation, images, and videos, in order to provide them with the necessary information for the analysis of the results and the completion of the corresponding questionnaires.

6.1.4 UC4.2 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move

1. Use case

The main objective of the use case is to allow reduced groups of individuals to participate on remote master class experiences through 5G connection, on-route, and fully immersive through head mounted display devices, and with remote immersive user interaction. The use case will provide the required means for the presenter to be stereoscopically captured and inserted in real or virtual scenarios including immersive graphic elements to improve presentations and to enable presenter and final users to communication ever specific graphics related to the explanations.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

Guarantee high-resolution video transmission and service continuity even when users are crossing the border. The solution uses an edge to deploy a CAM service involving a video server in order to redistribute video to all the connected clients from one stream and ensure connection on both sides of the border.

The use of slicing is beneficial in guaranteeing high bandwidth, needed for real-time game video reception and user synchronization.

For correct cross-border functionality, positioning is needed at both sides of the border.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service;
- real-time video server proxy can be deployed and used successfully on an edge server;

- the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow the video proxy relocation to guarantee seamless service delivery for multiple clients across borders;
- user's information can be exchanged within the servers in an interoperable way, also across borders;
- slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to bandwidth and reliability.

4. Use case scenarios

The following field trials are planned:

- First set of trials: transmission of collaboration data between two UEs (streaming laptop) and receiving HMD in cross-border environment.
- Second set of trials: Multi-user collaboration for users moving in vehicles across the border.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

PARTNERS INVOLVED:

- BRAINSTORM: Leader of the use case. Provides: content capture and streaming stage, containerized video proxy solution and the VR Player application;
- ATOS, CTTC: Validate the use cases in a cross-border multi-operator orchestration environment;
- TTU and ERICSSON: 5G network infrastructure

EQUIPMENT:

- **Capture and streaming server:** as the use case requires a real time video input for the testing, a streaming server will be placed outside the 5G infrastructure providing the continuous and "live" required video input. In case the 5G network infrastructure does not allow external connections for the tests, the capture and streaming server will be deployed inside the 5G network employing a Nvidia Jetson Nano.
- **Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs):** for showing the virtual scene with the integrated presenter to the users, including head tracking to allow the user immersivity on the scene.
- **High end laptops:** as the actual HMDs do not have the performance neither the connectivity needed for the trials, the rendering will be done externally on laptops, to which the HMD will be connected directly.
- **Smartphones:** In order to provide the laptops, the 5G required connectivity needed for the trials, the mobile devices from the UC 4.1 will be used as modem between the laptops and 5G network.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials location: CTTC – Barcelona. In addition to those tests explained above, CTTC lab will also support trials related to the integration of UC4.2 with the required enablers of CAM Services Platform.

The tests will be focused on the application compatibility and the evaluation of the 5G network capabilities before the field trials, specifically on measuring the network throughput and how it affects the user QoE.

The data will be captured by the laptops in order to check the network expected performance.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- At least 5 minutes route duration for optimal testing;
- recommended 220V power supply in the trial vehicle (car / ferry).

8. Location for field trials

- terrestrial tests: Estonia/Latvia border in Valga;
- maritime tests: Ferry between Tallin-Helsinki.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Data logged by the laptops.

- timestamp for each communication;
- VR client KPIs (Stream resolution, frame rate, bitrate)
- message delay;
- data packet size.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

Stakeholders:

- Pompeu Fabra University (UPF)
- Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

User involvement:

- Pompeu Fabra University (UPF)
- Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

As it not possible to get personnel from UPF and NTNU in the lab and field trials, the results will be presented to them in the way of documentation, images, and videos in order to provide them with the necessary information for the analysis of the results and the completion of the corresponding questionnaires.

6.2 Maritime Ecosystem

6.2.1 UC5.1 Connected Logistics

1. Use case

Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting.

Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, [i.e.](#), transportation needs to be monitored continuously via remote control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity

Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard device, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.

Figure 16. Use case 5.1 illustration (source Vediafi)

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The use case focuses on maritime transportation that operates between Finland and Estonia. In addition, the case highlights the maritime environment where the communication network quality and coverage are not as good as in on the land area, e.g., in the cities or main roads. In this use case, trials focus on the solution on how to enable continuous and high-quality connection in this maritime transport corridor. The solution will cover combination of 5G and multi-hop solutions and satellite connection.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

In status quo, ferry operators have 4G based solutions available and they offer free Wi-Fi for their passengers. For cargo customers, operators do not have specified communication services. The hypothesis for trials is that 5G- ROUTES will provide new and better communication solutions, which provide better quality and enable new services for customers. The hypothesis is also that the new solutions are economically sustainable.

4. Use case scenarios

In UC 5.1. trials the QoS of the 5G onshore multi-hop solution and satellite link will be analysed while crossing the Gulf of Finland, is tested. Focus of the trials is connectivity and capacity of available connections.

Use Case 5.1. aim is to test continuous connection during the ferry trip. The UC utilises on board devices, where vehicle is equipped with OBU and linked RTK-device, IoT sensors and one camera. RTK device is utilised to enable RTK metadata monitor, which further is used to analyse GNSS status information. Video camera and temperature sensor monitors vehicle status during the transportation. The OBU is connected to the ferry communication infrastructure, and it shares location, temperature and time data to backend systems via the 5G- ROUTES communication infrastructure. This data is used to analyse the QoS of connectivity. Aim of the tests is to monitor and measure the quality of service during the ferry trip, with various connectivity setups.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- Vediafi: connectivity testing/RTK metadata testing/ and use case lead;
- Eckerö Line: Vediafi subcontractor, provides one ferry as test platform;
- TBD: communication devices on ferry;
- TBD: network provider for ferry;
- Airbus: satellite communication for ferry;

- Brainstorm: link to passenger transport trials and lead of passenger use case 4.1;
- VTT: testing framework and field test support, link between logistics and V2X trials + support to WP2 positioning trials;
- Vedia test vehicle;
- Enide: tracking app-- potential extension.

6. Location for lab trials

Lab trials will be performed in Vedia lab and in Otaniemi/Espoo/Finland VTT lab in order make preparations for ferry trials.

- Vedia office/lab (Helsinki) + VTT test lab (Otaniemi/Espoo): system preparation and pre-testing of set-up;
- Vedia will create the baseline data and large-scale trial capabilities in collaboration with UC5.1. partners in Espoo;
- test network testing VTT (Espoo).

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- test devices inside the ferry and access to ferry infra;
- 5G- ROUTES communication environment on the ferry and shore (including multi-hop and satellite);
- ferry transport between Finland and Estonia and related ports;
- IoT devices will be connected to Vedia CaaS cloud system, from where data can be shared for external usage;
- Vedia cloud servers will provide statistics and logs for parameters;

8. Location for field trials

- Ferry trip between Helsinki and Tallinn: Vuosaari – Muuga connection;

9. Logging of data and logging process

- Vedia VCU/OBU devices and 5G-mobile with Vedia app are supporting data logging inside ferry with time stamp (if 5G on board network delivers radio signal to cargo space as planned) to support the PI's and defined trials;
- communication infrastructure inside ferry, data logging with time stamp;
- vehicle: 5G-device ID data linked with data synch to OBU, 5G-phone, RSU, IoT devices and VCU data;
- VCU/OBU: data logging with time stamp;
- IoT devices/VCU: data logging with time stamp;
- connectivity infrastructure/network during ferry trip: data logging with time stamp.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

- Eckerö Line;
- secondary vessel provider;
- connectivity service providers;
- relevant 5G ROUTES project partners (e.g VTT, Enide and Airbus);

- testing with Vedia own vehicles.

6.2.2 UC5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border

1. Use case

The use case aims to provide a continuous video and speech communication with the ferry's staff and also with the **harbour's** administration to lead to a safe trip for the passengers and also for the cargo that is transported inside the ferry. Lack of communication between the ferry and its staff at a cross border can possibly lead to human fatalities and damages to ferry. Use case 5.2 focuses on the provision of live streaming services between the captain and the ferry's staff so as a smooth trip can occur throughout the trip including cross border areas. UC 5.2 offers the ability to cover cross-border issues, including seamless communication of high bandwidth video streaming during the multihop communication between **harbour to** ferry and between ferry to another ferry and seamless support to the captain throughout the trip.

Figure 17: Video live streaming between ferries and/or harbour

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

For the maritime technology there is a requirement to have a service continuity along the whole ferry route from the **harbour** and from one ferry to another especially when they cross a border. Therefore, the 5G coverage along the route needs to be sufficient to provide service continuity. Additionally, inside the ferry, due to heavy iron construction, it is difficult to support the coverage, therefore the network coverage also inside the ferry needs to be sufficient.

3. Hypotheses to be tested

The 5G-ROUTES needs to provide good coverage in the sea route between ferries when they cross a border and good coverage inside the ferry to support the needed service continuity for video streaming applications between ferries and between a ferry and a harbour. the high data originated from the cameras and the time elapsed at a cross border need to be measured:

- the data rate measured when the cameras connected to an OBU are transmitting between ferries and between ferry and harbour;
- service continuity elapse time at a cross border.

4. Use case scenarios

This use case will first be tested in the local lab, then tested at the ferry route. The roadmap is as follows:

- Lab trial #1: high data rate sent from the camera of the OBU;
- First phase of the field trial: service continuity during the route of the ferry at a cross border;
- Second phase of the field trial: high data rate DL and UL at a cross border in the sea.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- WINGS: Use case Leader. Developer of smart gateway and video application;
- Vedia: provision of a truck to host the OBU and video application client.

6. Location for lab trials

The lab trials are performed at WINGS lab in Athens.

Lab trials at WINGS lab will test eMBB type of traffic and service continuity to be tested and demonstrated as it is described below:

- Data rate measurements in WINGS lab,
- Data rate measurements when a cross border exists between two different operators in the same country.

KPIs to be demonstrated at the maritime trials and validated:

- QoS degradation < 5% during cross-border mobility,
- Zero dropped sessions during cross-border mobility,
- Data rate downlink and uplink.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

- 5G coverage throughout the ferry route,
- 5G testbed and network coverage inside the ferry and along the route,
- Vedia's van availability,
- WINGS cloud servers will provide a UI for statistics and logs data,

8. Location for field trials

- Ferry trip from Helsinki to Tallinn;

9. Logging of data and logging process

- Live streaming data from the OBU, and application server will be logged for this use case,
- OBU with video camera equipped,
- Video simulator tool,
- User interface to show the start of the application and KPIs values if TWP cannot be deployed.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

End users such as professional and/or ferry passengers will take part in the use case testing/trials and will interact with the developed user interface (via laptops and/or smartphones). For confidentiality and ease of access purposes the people involved in the trials will be preferably employed by one of the project partners. A clear and understandable consent form will be provided to the human experimenters informing them about the data to be logged. Data logging follows GDPR guidelines and is anonymized to protect the privacy of the human experimenters. No specific information regarding each user will be collected besides their location (GPS data from smartphone or vehicle) and potential video recordings of the tests. As of that tests will involve the following partners:

- Eckerö Line;
- Port actors;
- Testing with Vedia's vehicles;
- WINGS OBU and application server.

6.3 Discontinued Use Cases

Based on feedback received from the reviewers, the project was focused on use cases with cross-border issues, involving maritime and terrestrial ecosystem (road use cases). The rail use case was discontinued, as the same infrastructure, which had to be deployed, could not be used for both rail and road. Also use case UC3.2, for which the cross-border issues were minimal, was discontinued. UC2.2 was discontinued due to the similarity with other use cases, and the planned design did not include any CAM services. The use cases were tested in labs, and these tests are reported in D3.8.

6.3.1 UC2.2 Traffic Jam Chauffeur

1. Use case

This use case focuses on highly automated vehicles that would operate on motorways reaching the cross-border junction, in which the driver is not required for vehicular control. The application integrates and provides active lane guidance and automatic braking and acceleration, both of which take additional traffic information into account.

2. Cross-border issues and solutions

The main cross-border issue is to guarantee service continuity for awareness message transmission. The solution is to make use of the situational awareness CAM service, located either on an edge server or the cloud.

High accuracy localization is needed on both sides of the border across all traffic participants for the best performance in reacting to external events (VRUs and traffic jams).

3. Hypotheses to be tested

- The 5G-ROUTES enablers allow to deploy the platoon management service seamlessly (in local breakout configuration);

- the 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enables allow seamless handover and continuity of the service;
- the end-to-end latency is within the targets;
- slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders;
- high positioning accuracy for supporting traffic awareness is available at both sides of the border.

4. Use case roadmap

The following trials are planned for evaluating the developed use case applications:

- Lab trial #1: create initial HD maps of areas where trials are to take place, test relevant V2X functionality and sensors for cooperative manoeuvres (radar, LIDAR and GNSS-RTK receiver).
- Lab trial #2: refine HD maps, test lane-following and lane-change behaviour on the Bīķernieki racetrack.
- Field trial #1: perform simulated traffic jam detection in a home routing configuration.
- Lab trial #3: test vehicle reactions to acquired awareness messages (slowing down, lane change).
- Field trial #2: situationally aware driving driving on closed roads in Valga with simulated traffic and VRUs.

5. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

- EDI: develop cooperative driving-related applications and services, supply two electric vehicles (equipped with LIDAR, radar, camera, GNSS-RTK, 5G communication system, drive-by-wire system and on-board computer) capable of automated driving.
- CERTH: develop CCAM Infrastructure and services.
- VEDECOM, VTT: provide additional connected vehicle.
- SWARCO: develop connected road infrastructure in Valka/Valga.

6. Location for lab trials, and use of lab trial data for evaluation

Lab trials are mainly performed on the Bīķernieki racetrack. Small-scale tests are also done in EDI premises, where a small intersection and roads with lane-markings are available, in addition to a commercial 5G network.

Data from tests (sensor and localization data, communication performance) is recorded for PI analysis.

7. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

Closed road, controllable environment, road with multiple lanes, cross walk, VRUs, vehicles.

8. Location for large-scale trials

The large-scale trials are planned to be performed on the Bīķernieki racetrack or the E264 highway near Valka/Valga.

9. Logging of data and logging process

Logging utilizing ROS based ecosystem, i.e., using rosbag files with synchronized data.

10. Stakeholder and user involvement

The trials will not include end-user involvement. Local stakeholders will provide their feedback during the trials.

6.3.2 UC3.2 Connected Maintenance

1. Use case

The UC 3.2 is built on mMTC service of 5G network as there will be very large number of devices expected to use this service. The primary objective of the Connected Maintenance use case (UC3.2) is to enable real time tracking of connected vehicles status from operation and maintenance point of view.

Connected vehicular onboard diagnostics (OBD) system will be used to track vehicular parameters and status. Parameter collection and reporting system will be developed which will be combined into a preventive maintenance framework. This framework will combine OBD parameter collecting, OBD parameter reporting, parameter analysis and parameter prediction algorithms. TTU will create, install, and configure controller device for collecting OBD parameters as well as communicating with cloud databases through Telia's network. Predictive maintenance algorithms will be developed in order to predict future behaviour of the connected vehicular.

2. Use case roadmap

- Lab test #1 (TTU 5G Testbed): Verification of OBU and interfaces to OBD and IoT network infrastructure. Purpose: Validate OBU functionality and ODB data reading/filtering
- Lab test #2 (TTU 5G Testbed): Cloud infrastructure verification and message transmission. Purpose: Enable the Cumulocity cloud platform, MQTT functionality.
- Lab test #3 (TTU 5G Testbed): Assure that the full system works correctly. Purpose: Validation of data analysis and predictive algorithm.
- Localized trial #1 (Valga/Valka): Data Acquisition from a vehicle and transfer to the cloud. Purpose: Technical verification of the trials, data transmission and processing verification
- Localized trial #2 (Valga/Valka): Full functional verification. Purpose: Cross- border service continuity testing, IoT roaming testing
- Extended trial #3 (Valga/Valka). Full functional verification. Purpose: final validation.

3. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

Partners and Roles

- ERICSSON: 5G Infrastructure provider and developer of CCAM infrastructure;
- TELIA: MNO, Cloud Platform provider (Cumulocity Cloud);
- TTU: CCAM infrastructure developer, ML algorithm developer;
- ENIDE: ML algorithm developer for predicting driving style;
- EDI: EV provider, On-Board Diagnostic data reading port availability;

Equipment/Infrastructure and Algorithms Plan

- 2 OBUs developed by TTU;
- Cumulocity Cloud installation with MQTT broker ;

- OBU software by TTU;
- EV parameter reading and filtering by EDI and TTU;
- ML algorithms by TTU and ENIDE installed and tested in TTU 5G Testbed in Tallinn.

4. Location for lab trials, and use of lab trial data for evaluation

UC 3.2 Connected Maintenance lab trials are conducted in TTU's 5G-IoT Testbed in Tallinn:

- Reading sensor data, OBD-II reader is used to filter CANbus messages, the filtering helps to use defined number of parameters so that we do not overload processor which will be used behind the OBD reader;
- testing OBD-II reader both in gasoline and EV cars, defining suitable parameters;
- transmitting sensor data through mMTC connection, ping tests will be used for testing IoT connection and also connection to the cloud server;
- MQTT broker and client communication setup and testing between OBU and Cloud server;
- storing sensor data in analytics database (database on cloud), sensor data filtering;
- running real-time predictive analytics (ML algorithms);
- estimating connected car maintenance needs;
- comparing number of methods for analysing the trends of parameters and then to predict early enough to avoid major malfunctioning.

5. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

UC 3.2 Connected Maintenance for the trials (Valga – Valka):

- 5G IoT network with connection to Cumulocity Cloud -- -- this will enable service delivery and continuity for cross-border scenario;
- mMTC slice in 5G network for IoT connectivity.

6. Location for large-scale trials

Valga – Valka city cross-border motorway E264,

7. Logging of data and logging process

OBU will log data collected from the car/vehicle,

Data sent to the Cloud will be logged/stored in Cloud,

Data stored on the Cloud will be downloaded for the purpose of backup and necessary postprocessing.

8. Stakeholder and user involvement

Car maintenance companies could be informed about maintenance status, their feedback could be included when handling vehicles maintenance needs.

Insurance companies could be informed about driving style.

This use case involves following stakeholders Citizens, car OEM suppliers, automotive maintenance, car OEMs

The end user is the most concerned by this use case which will increase the effectiveness of maintenance on his car.

6.3.3 UC5.3 Continuous Railway Infrastructure Monitoring with Optical Sensors

1. Use case

Modern railway infrastructure like any other complex mechanical system requires a day-to-day monitoring and maintenance. As railways network is stretched across vast territories it requires fully automated or semi-automated technologies to capture, process, reason on, and store monitoring data for continuous (long term) infrastructure monitoring. Modern dept (3D) cameras in combination with LIDAR and other sensor technologies enable new application scenarios with potential positive business impact in the future as it will enable cost efficient railway network monitoring and predictive maintenance applications.

It is proposed to deploy modern depth camera and LIDAR on the train to collect and stream over 5G network sensor data for further data processing. Additionally, these sensors are flexible and will enable various data streaming scenarios at various bandwidths starting from few megabits per second and concluding with 200 Mbps and more. This setup will allow us to provide constant and variable large volume data stream for 5G network performance, stability, and many other test scenarios.

Use case initial testing is planned in route from Valga railway station (Estonia) to Lugaži railway station (Latvia). The train will start its route in Estonian where sensors will stream their readings via Estonian mobile network operator Telia infrastructure and after border crossing the network provider will switch to Latvian mobile network operator LMT infrastructure. It is not decided yet where the sensor data processing will take place as there are multiple options, like, Edge, Edge-Cloud and Cloud scenario which has their own benefits and drawbacks. One of our objectives is to practically try out, evaluate, analyse, and choose the best suitable data processing method/solution architecture for our desired application scenario.

2. Use case roadmap

It is planned to have 4 trials where we will answer the following questions:

Trial 1- Dept camera and LIDAR performance evaluation on railway infrastructure monitoring with local data processing and storage. We will evaluate sensor data quality and application potential for infrastructure monitoring applications. This sensor test will be held in LAB environment and on railway paths near Riga.

Trial 2 – Dept camera and LIDAR data streaming over mobile network (3G,4G and 5G) to cloud (organization data center) where data will be stored and analysed for further applications. We will evaluate data streaming capabilities and latency. It is planned to compare TCP/IP and UDP protocol performance in this application scenario.

Trial 3 – Dept camera and LIDAR data streaming over 5G network to edge-cloud computing node located in 5G base station for data storage, pre-processing and further processed data transfer over mobile network to cloud. We will evaluate edge-cloud data processing scenario to identify potential improvements and actual computing power and storage amount requirements. In this trial 5G network precise geolocation capabilities will be tested to improve sensor data referencing precision.

Trial 4 – Dept camera and LIDAR data streaming over 5G network to edge-cloud computing node located in 5G base station, data processing on the edge-cloud node, data streaming to other users for visualisation in 5G

network. This trial will combine all scenarios into single one. With particular focus on processed data distribution to parties located in the same mobile network cell as well as internet users.

We expect to use Enabler interfaces that support precise GPS coordinates for more precise data referencing.

3. Partners involved; equipment used in the use case (vehicles, smart phones, infrastructure sensors)

The following partners and equipment are involved:

- PV- train, railway infrastructure, dept camera, LIDAR and local computing node;
- LMT and Telia – Mobile network infrastructure, routers, base station computing hardware and smartphones

4. Location for lab trials, and use of lab trial data for evaluation

Lab trials are planned in LAB environment and on railway paths near Riga. During these trials LIDAR and Depth camera readings will be collected and analysed to identify required hardware parameters, e.g., camera field of view, range, required data transfer rate (MB, GB), frames per second etc. Based on identified network infrastructure throughput and latency requirements trial testbed/network infrastructure performance will be evaluated.

5. Specific requirements for the trial environment (e.g., closed roads, roads with multiple lanes)

The trials can be executed only on railway infrastructure. Mobile network throughput should be sufficient for stable sensor data readings transfer. For tests outside testbed, we are planning to implement temporal data buffer that will be emptied when mobile network data throughput will be sufficient for large amount data transfer.

6. Location for large-scale trials

Large-scale trials will be executed on railway infrastructure near Riga.

7. Logging of data and logging process

It is planned to log mobile network performance to identify minimum mobile network throughput requirements for real life LIDAR and Depth camera data streaming applications.

8. Stakeholder and User involvement

It is planned to interview SIA „LDZ infrastruktūra” (railway tracks operator) infrastructure monitoring department experts to identify and discuss LIDAR and Depth camera sensor data application for continues infrastructure monitoring and potential automation scenarios. Discussions will be organized in several rounds where each round will be dedicated to specific topic. Now the following topics are planned: current railway monitoring process and current challenges, LIDAR and Depth camera application examples and generated output, real life trial results presentation, potential further application scenarios

7 Conclusions

This deliverable is the second report on the testing framework. Deliverable D1.7 gave an initial description of the test framework at the start of the project. This deliverable, D1.12, provides an update, including the procedures for collecting data.

The nature of the CCAM use cases puts stringent requirements to the testing environment, especially for automated driving manoeuvres, like a closed traffic environment with multiple lanes covered by multiple networks.

The technical validation will be performed during the field trials, as well as a large-scale trial on the corridor Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki. However, due to changes in the project and delays in the availability of 5G SA roaming, only a single trial cycle is planned. This trial cycle will consist of two short phases: in a first phase, concentrating on simple scenarios focusing on measuring simplified use cases are evaluated, and the focus is on analysing the service disruption during cross-border handover and validating the integration of the use cases interaction with the CAM Services Platform in a real environment. In the second phase, the more complex use case scenarios will be evaluated.

The use cases are organised in two ecosystems: the terrestrial and the maritime ecosystem. The use cases from the terrestrial ecosystem will be trialled at the E265 border crossing in Valga/Valka and automated driving tests may be performed at a virtual crossing at the Bikernieki race track in Riga. The maritime use cases will be trialled on a ferry between Vuosaari and Muuga.

Based on the list of identified Performance Indicators (PIs), the data, which have to be logged, are identified. Both use case agnostic data will be collected, as well as use case specific data. Data will be collected both at transport and at application level. The applications hence have to implement the required logging, for being able to calculate the PIs. In addition, all network elements have to be synchronised with each other, in order to be able to measure latencies accurately.

Collected data will be stored in the Tenant Web Portal, which is part of the 5G-ROUTES platform, and which is described in more detail in D2.7. The use case leaders will extract the data from the web for performing the analysis and calculate the PIs, which are then fed back in the Tenant Web Portal, where the composite indicators, defined in D1.9, are calculated and visualised.

The whole data chain, from data collection, importing and storing the collected data in the Tenant Web Portal, calculation of PIs and visualisation of composite indicators in the Tenant Web Portal, will be validated during the first set of lab tests, and refined before the first set of localised trials. The final testing framework will be reported in D1.8.

Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment. The commercialisation validation process will create anticipatory business plans for two solutions that extend 5G for the different environments of cross-border. The business impact assessment will deliver the estimated impact and cost-benefit for the developed ecosystems, validated by both internal and external to the project stakeholders. Furthermore, on the basis of the 5G Architecture and 5G CAM Infrastructure developed in the project, the interoperability impact and deployment potential will be investigated in close collaboration with the project technology providers. Results of the business validation will be reported in the new D5.2 (merged D5.2 and D5.3) "Business validation of the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems".

8 References

- [1] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.1 Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0
- [2] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.3 Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0
- [3] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0
- [4] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D1.9 Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0
- [5] 5G-ROUTES (2020) D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0
- [6] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D5.1 Commercialisation marketing plan for 5G enabled business models for CAM v1.0
- [7] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.7 Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment v1
- [8] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM 1.0
- [9] 5G-SOLUTIONS, 5G-solutions for European Citizens, <https://www.5gsolutionsproject.eu/>
- [10] Deming, W. Edwards (1986). Out of the crisis. Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for Advanced Engineering Study.
- [11] 5G-TOURS, <https://5gtours.eu/>
- [12] 5G-EVE, 5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials, <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>
- [13] 5G-MOBIX, Driving forward Connected & Automated Mobility, <https://www.5g-mobix.com/>
- [14] FESTA Handbook, Version 7 (2018, December), Retrieved from <https://connectedautomateddriving.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/FESTA-Handbook-Version-7.pdf>
- [15] TRUSTS, Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space, <https://www.trusts-data.eu/>
- [16] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.1 AI-Assisted Cross-Domain MEC and Integration Fabric for CAM services v1.0
- [17] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.3 AI-based end-to-end slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services v1.0
- [18] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological Enablers for CAM v1.0
- [19] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D3.1 Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM
- [20] 5G-ROUTES (2021) D3.3 Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0
- [21] Macharis C., Verbeke A., De Brucker K. (2004) The strategic evaluation of new technologies through Multicriteria analysis: the Advisors case, In: Bekiaris, E., Nakanishi Y. (Eds.), Economic Impacts of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Innovations and Case Studies. Research in Transportation Economics. Elsevier, Vol. 8, pp. 443–462.
- [22] ITU-R report M.2410-0 “Minimum requirements related to technical performance for IMT-2020
- [23] K. Katsaros et al. (2019) 5G-MOBIX D2.5, Initial evaluation KPIs and metrics. Retrieved from <https://www.5g-mobix.com/assets/files/5G-MOBIX-D2.5-Initial-evaluation-KPIs-and-metrics-V1.4.pdf>
- [24] 5G for Europe: An Action Plan. European Commission, SWD (2016), 306.
- [25] European Commission (2019), STRIA Roadmap on Connected and Automated Transport: Road, Rail and Waterborne, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation.
- [26] Brooke, J. (1996). SUS: A “Quick and Dirty” Usability Scale. In P. Jordan, B. Thomas, I. McClelland, & B. Weerdmeester (Eds.), Usability Evaluation In Industry (pp. 189-194). London: CRC Press
- [27] Schrepp, M., Hinderks, A., & Thomaschewski, J. r. (2017). Construction of a Benchmark for the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence, 4(Regular Issue), 40-44. doi:10.9781/ijimai.2017.445.
- [28] Dehn, D. M. (2008). Assessing the Impact of Automation on the Air Traffic Controller: The SHAPE Questionnaires. Air Traffic Control Quarterly, 16(2), 127-146. doi:10.2514/atcq.16.2.127.

- [29]Kaan, J. (2017).""User Acceptance of Autonomous Vehicles: Factors and Implication"" , M.S. thesis, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands.
- [30]5G-ROUTES (2021) D5.7 Data Management Plan v1.0
- [31]5G-MOBIX (2022) D3.7 Final Report on Development, Integration and Roll-out
- [32]Kaitotek (2022) Qosium, <https://www.kaitotek.com/qosium>
- [33]De Brucker, K., Macharis, C. (2011), Best Things First. The Application of Multi-Criteria Analysis to Derive Implementation Priorities for Innovative Road Safety Measures. *Infrastructure and Safety in a Collaborative World*, pp. 305-325
- [34]Keysight (2023), Nemo Outdoor 5G NR Drive Test Solution, <https://www.keysight.com/fi/en/product/NTA50000B/nemo-outdoor-5g-nr-drive-test-solution.html>
- [35]ETSI TS 138 331-V16.13.0 (2023) 5G; NR; Radio Resource Control (RRC); Protocol specification (3GPP TS 38.331 version 16.13.0 Release 16)